

Examining the Effect of AI Writing Tools on Grade 7 and 8 Learners' Cohesion
in a Private School in Lebanon

by

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Abstract

The current study analyzed the use of artificial intelligence (AI) writing tools to improve writing coherence of seventh and eighth graders at a private school in Lebanon. At this level of education, learners face considerable barriers regarding the breakdown of ideas and writing cohesion. To understand this phenomenon, the study collected qualitative data from both learners and teachers about their experiences with writing challenges and the methods used to solve them.

This study used qualitative methods, which include interviews conducted with learners and focus groups with the teachers and the learners. This strategy helped to understand better the underlying issues of problems related to writing cohesion and the attempts made to resolve them.

Besides, this study explored the use of AI writing tools to suggest possible fixes to common coherence problems. Faculty interviews assessed their usage of AI writing tools and learners' responses to prompts provided by these systems. In addition, the study looked into the existing practices and researched how AI could be used in curriculum writing instruction integration.

This research addresses a significant gap in the literature where there is hardly any analysis of the application of AI writing tools in Lebanon's educational framework. Due to the increasing relevance of AI in education, this examination highlights the lack of employment AI has with the Lebanese classroom as well as the need for more exploration in this field. These results explain how AI technologies can enhance the coherence of writing that is essential for instructors, decision's makers, and learners.

Educators can use such information to change educational practices, develop curricula, and formulate policies that seek to enhance writing in all subjects. The importance of this research

also lies in the integration of AI in writing pedagogy as a possible means to resolve a fundamental problem that many educators encounter.

Keywords: Writing Coherence ; Artificial Intelligence in Education; Middle School Writing Skills ; Educational Technology ; AI-Assisted Writing

المستخلص

تتناول هذه الدراسة استخدام أدوات الكتابة المعتمدة على الذكاء الاصطناعي لتحسين ترابط الكتابة لدى طلاب الصفين السابع والثامن في مدرسة خاصة في لبنان. يواجه الطلاب في هذه المرحلة من التعليم تحديات كبيرة في تنظيم الأفكار وتحقيق التماسك في كتاباتهم. ولتفهم هذه الظاهرة، جمعت الدراسة بيانات نوعية من الطلاب والمعلمين حول تجاربهم مع صعوبات الكتابة والأساليب المستخدمة لمعالجتها.

استخدمت الدراسة منهجية نوعية شملت مقابلات فردية مع الطلاب ومجموعات تركيز مع المعلمين والطلاب. ساعدت هذه الاستراتيجية في فهم أعمق للمشكلات الأساسية المتعلقة بترابط الكتابة ومحاولات حلها. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، استكشفت الدراسة استخدام أدوات الكتابة المدعومة بالذكاء الاصطناعي كوسيلة لاقتراح حلول للمشكلات الشائعة المتعلقة بالترابط النصي. كما قيمت مقابلات المعلمين استخدامهم لهذه الأدوات وردود أفعال الطلاب تجاه النصوص الناتجة عنها. علاوة على ذلك، بحثت الدراسة في الممارسات الحالية ودرست كيفية دمج الذكاء الاصطناعي في تعليم مهارات الكتابة ضمن المناهج الدراسية.

تعالج هذه الدراسة فجوة بحثية مهمة تتمثل في نقص الدراسات حول تطبيق أدوات الذكاء الاصطناعي في النظام التعليمي اللبناني. وبالنظر إلى تزايد أهمية الذكاء الاصطناعي في التعليم، تسلط الدراسة الضوء على محدودية استخدام هذه الأدوات في الصفوف اللبنانية، والحاجة إلى المزيد من البحث في هذا المجال. تبين النتائج كيف يمكن لتقنيات الذكاء الاصطناعي أن تعزز ترابط الكتابة، وهو جانب أساسي يهتم المعلمين وصنّاع القرار والمتعلمين على حد سواء.

يمكن للمعلمين الاستفادة من هذه النتائج لتعديل ممارساتهم التربوية، وتطوير المناهج، ووضع السياسات التي تهدف إلى تحسين مهارات الكتابة في مختلف المواد الدراسية. تكمن أهمية هذا البحث أيضاً في دمج الذكاء الاصطناعي في تعليم الكتابة كوسيلة ممكنة لمعالجة مشكلة أساسية تواجه العديد من المعلمين.

الكلمات المفتاحية:

ترابط الكتابة؛ الذكاء الاصطناعي في التعليم؛ مهارات الكتابة في المرحلة المتوسطة؛ التكنولوجيا التعليمية؛ الكتابة بمساعدة الذكاء الاصطناعي.

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Dedication

To my mother who remains a constant source of strength and whose enduring love along with her prayers has seen me through difficulties.

To my father, for inspiring me to achieve my goals and instilling in me the belief that no dream is too grand.

To my sister , for showing faith in me and providing me with relentless support that motivated me to strive for greater heights.

To my husband , for his calm support and boundless understanding, granting me the freedom I needed as I delved into the books.

To my children whose affection and understanding as well as the selfless sacrifices they made without questioning ‘why’ has aided me greatly.

And to everyone who in their own way, be it through word, presence or spirit, has supported me during this journey, my gratitude.

This milestone does not solely reside on my achievements but rather all of theirs and mine.

Definition of Terms

There are key terms used throughout this research study:

AI Writing Tools: Software applications that use artificial intelligence to help with different aspects of writing, like grammar correction, style improvement and coherence enhancement are known as AI writing tools. These tools usually have features such as automated proofreading, sentence restructuring suggestions and real-time feedback on the quality of writing.

Cohesion: In writing, cohesion is a term used for the flow and connectivity of ideas within a text. It involves using cohesive devices (like conjunctions, pronouns and transition words) so that sentences and paragraphs logically connect with each other making the text read smoothly.

Qualitative Approach: The qualitative approach in research seeks to understand phenomena descriptively or interpretatively from participants' perspectives by collecting non-numerical data such as interviews, written texts observations etc., hence gaining insights into their experiences, beliefs, behaviors among others.

Thematic Analysis: Thematic analysis is an approach employed in qualitative studies aimed at identifying patterns or themes within qualitative datasets through coding organizing data into themes then interpreting them to provide insight regarding research questions posed during the study process

Cognitive Constructivism: A learning theory emphasizing cognitive processes in understanding knowledge construction is known as Cognitive constructivism that posits that learners actively build their own understanding about the world based on experiences they have gone through coupled with interactions made throughout life while also recognizing its internalization structure aspect involved during this process

Sociocultural Theory: Vygotsky's sociocultural theory suggests that cultural context and social interaction are crucial for cognitive development. Collaborative learning, as well as how individuals learn influenced by these factors are highlighted by this theory.

Validity And Reliability – In research, validity refers to whether a study measures what it intends accurately while reliability means consistent findings over time under varying conditions thus both must be present in order for results produced by any given piece of scientific work to be considered credible and trustworthy.

Sampling Design And Plan – Selecting study participants including inclusion criteria plus selection method constitutes sampling design whilst detailing participant selection organization control experimental groups among others forms part of your overall sampling strategy

Pre-Post Intervention Surveys – Gather baseline data using pre-intervention surveys conducted prior to intervention(s) such as AI Writing Tools followed by post-intervention surveys carried out afterwards which evaluate changes brought about due interventions applied.

Ethical Considerations -Research ethics require protection towards participants' rights/wellbeing i.e confidentiality maintenance anonymity assurance informed consent acquisition addressing possible risks/biases involved during entire research process etc.

Automated Essay Scoring Systems -Software applications designed specifically for assessing written essays objectively consistently based upon criteria like grammar coherence and overall quality evaluation include automated essay scoring systems.

Writing Cohesion And Coherence – While writing cohesion relates to how different parts within a text are linked together creating unity throughout; writing coherence refers instead towards logical progression clarity throughout ensuring sense-making effective communication intended message.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Understanding written text language cohesion is very important, particularly to beginners of English as a second language (Hinkel, 2011). Writing cohesion is vital for these learners' understanding. Learners can organize their ideas more effectively and follow the logical flow of information when they write cohesively (Crossley et al., 2016). In order to cultivate the skills that foster cohesive writing, appropriate educational practices must be executed adeptly (Lee et al., 2022). Despite AI writing tools being contemporary methodologies, there is a lack of interest toward their application in educational settings, although they are essential for creating cohesion in writing (Marzuki et al., 2023). Traditional teaching methods cannot provide timely and specific feedback that significantly enhances cohesion in writing. Therefore, this gap calls for innovative approaches to teaching writing that integrate with technology (Wu et al., 2023).

These challenges should be addressed because combining AI writing tools with traditional forms can have a broader scope of learning. Concerning teachers' delivery of personalized instructions through which they can rectify any weaknesses in cohesion, AI writing tools give immediate feedback on the mistakes made concerning coherence and context, making them helpful and helping them realize what they need to teach precisely (Toufaha, 2024). Thus, better integration

translates into better writing skills, enhanced grades and increased self-assurance in learners' speeches (Allen et al., 2021).

The study focused on the integration of customary approaches with the use of AI writing applications to improve the coherence of essays composed by learners at the intermediate level. Learners' written work was predicted to be more coherent in cases where artificial intelligence was applied together with traditional methods of teaching. The researcher explored learners' views from private schools on the issues concerning cohesiveness and demonstrated the role of artificial intelligence in improving writing skills (Siti Zulfa, 2023). According to studies, learners' written work improves coherence if traditional teaching methods and help from Artificial Intelligence are combined (Seufert et al., 2021). Building on his findings, instructional strategies in language teaching have been evolving for years in relation to various educational contexts. According to Litman (2024), it seems that the combinations of teacher feedback and AI support will be beneficial to learners with L2 learning challenges.

1.2 Organization of the Study

The researcher organized the study into five chapters. The first chapter, which started with an abstract, began by introducing the research. After that, it showed the context of the study, rationale, problem statement and purpose, research questions and hypotheses, and the significance of the study to educators and learners. Chapter two portrayed the literature review of the study. It will discuss L2 learners' writing coherence challenges. It also depicted how teacher feedback allows them to create text connectedness in their drafts. In addition, it considered using AI techniques in academic settings. Consequently, the efficiency of the artificial intelligence

tools were examined through the research that was conducted at a private school in Lebanon. Finally, chapter three described the methodology that was used. This chapter expounded the research paradigm, research approach, research design, population and sampling, data collection techniques, analysis and interpretation of the collected data, validity and ethical considerations amended in carrying out this research.

1.3 Context of the Study

The current research aimed to study the role of AI writing tools in enhancing writing coherence in grade 7 and 8 learners enrolled in a school in Beirut. This investigation was part of the larger perspective of improving the educational achievements of learners whereby the digital tools along with conventional pedagogical approaches are studied as a means to assist learners in structuring their arguments, improving their paragraphs transitions, and enhancing the overall design of their written work. While targeting the middle school education systems where most pupils had challenges of writing logically and fluently, this study sought to address the gap of understanding the effects of AI writing tools on ratio attainment and other elements of academic achievement and their implications on subsequent teaching and learning. By taking opinions from learners as well as teachers, the study provided useful insights into the role of AI in education in general and the teaching of writing in particular.

historical background of the school . In 1975, quality education was brought to many learners by establishing a school in Beirut. Initially, it was conceived as a community-based school that would thrive to promote academic excellence and personal growth in a caring atmosphere. Over many years, it has expanded in size, facilities, and reputation. It has transformed from humble

beginnings into a respected educational institution known for its broad syllabus and dedication to student development.

school overview. The current school's mission statement is to create an environment that fosters learners' intellectual curiosity, creativity, and critical thinking. The vision is to prepare citizens who are ready for any global environment through a balanced and inclusive education system so far. The school currently enrolls boys and girls from KG1 up to Grade 12 from diverse backgrounds. The student-teacher ratio is such that each student receives personalized attention, creating a supportive learning climate.

curriculum. English language books are foreign-based but primarily aligned with the Lebanese national curriculum. However, grades nine (9) and twelve (12) strictly conform to Lebanese national standards since their program only prepares learners for official examinations in those respective grades. In addition, this institution is also working towards being credited by Cognia to show its dedication to maintaining high education standards. These encompass a focus on academic performance, nurturing a well-rounded individual for society, and diverse programs. The school's educational program outlines that extra-curricular activities, a well-developed character, and academic success are given priority. Learners have access to gifted counseling sessions, tutorials, or specialized programs tailored for gifted learners. Moreover, there are other regional competitions conducted by the British Council or Model United Nations (MUN) which draw participants from this school and therefore, help them broaden their skills internationally.

educational environment. Technology integration is one of the mainstays of teaching and learning in this school. The schoolrooms are equipped with contemporary educational materials,

and the educators employ digital assets to make their teaching more effective. The teachers have extensive qualifications and participate in continuous professional learning programs to keep them updated on emerging trends in education and instructional approaches. The school implements differentiated teaching and individual support to ensure an all-embracing education program. There are numerous ways in which formative and summative appraisals are used to continuously evaluate learners' progress and realize what they have attained.

challenges and reforms. Improving student learning and writing coherence in intermediate grades is one of the biggest challenges that schools face. Teachers have attempted to increase educational results. For instance, improving teaching strategies and professional development for teachers. Moreover, the school is part of the more outstanding Lebanese educational system. Nevertheless, this school still needs to try AI writing tools.

specifics related to writing and cohesion. In this school, writing education is highly focused on all levels of studies but is most stressed for middle grades. Inconsistency poses a problem for many writers who fail to link ideas properly or use connective solid words and phrases. Some strategies for improving writing skills are workshops that concentrate on specific areas of improvement and revising drafts based on comments given during peer reviews. Teachers provide feedback personally tailored to each student and offer opportunities for self-correction through different forms of input supplied by others, including themselves. The institution uses different methods to assess diverse aspects of written work; for instance, rubrics can be employed while assessing different writing assignments at various stages or levels within a single assignment or across multiple tasks over time to track growth toward cohesive written expression.

This study was aimed at being the pioneer in examining AI writing tools' utility in this educational context. Considering how these tools merge with conventional teaching methods, this investigation will attempt to strengthen the cohesiveness in writing among grade seven and eight learners. This research incorporated input from learners and teachers to get perspectives regarding the effectiveness of AI-supported writing instruction in guiding future educational practices.

1.4 Rationale

Focusing on an issue of concern is a gap in the literature that pertains to the perseverance of Lebanese private school learners. The literature review revealed that writing cohesion is an expression of communication and a skill related to one's level of academic success (Astari, 2021). A student's writing cohesion depicts how a written work 'flows' in a logical and clear manner and is an important skill particularly in the 7th and 8th grades as learners begin to refine their writing skills (Harris et al., 2012).

A broader range of current research on writing cohesion tends not to examine how it manifests itself within specific educational contexts like that of Lebanon's private schools. Furthermore, although many different instructional strategies have been shown by researchers to be successful at improving overall written expression abilities among learners with diverse needs across all grade levels, none has looked specifically into their effectiveness for addressing such issues using AI-based tools designed explicitly for these purposes alone. This lack of attention given towards integrating them into classroom practice where appropriate represents a significant

oversight since without proper training teachers will not know what works best under different circumstances (Graham & Perin, 2007; Sheu, 2019).

Addressing these gaps is important because increasing understanding about how we can improve our learners' ability to write coherently would greatly enhance both their academic performance as well as ability to communicate effectively. If there isn't targeted research done then educators might not have any good strategies available that could help deal with this issue leading them to engage in suboptimal instruction which results in poor student outcomes.

The proposed study sought to address some of the gaps mentioned above by determining whether AI writing tools are effective at enhancing student writers' cohesiveness within the context of Lebanese private schools. It used qualitative methods involving both teacher and student perspectives to assess the impact made by artificial intelligence applications on this aspect of written discourse. The findings from such an inquiry should contribute knowledge about problems relating to coherent expression in written work while suggesting workable solutions. Moreover, it would enrich existing literature base thus informing pedagogical practices and promoting culturally relevant teaching among school systems worldwide.

1.5 Statement of the Problem

Despite efforts made to teach writing skills, learners in grade 7 and 8 at Lebanon's private schools continue to struggle with essay writing problems. They are unable to formulate essays that flow logically and are structured appropriately. Evidence gathered from Lebanon shows that many learners attending private schools in grades 7 and 8 lack the ability to demonstrate basic

skills of coherence and cohesiveness in their writing. They write poorly organized and incoherent essays despite attempts made in the past to help them develop these essential skills.

The fact that their essays seem to lack coherence suggests that their ability to perform academically as well as communicate effectively is compromised, a fact that corresponds with ESL writing cohesion concerns established in Hinkel's (2004) study. Other studies further underline the importance of writing cohesively as an absolute necessity for a student's academic achievement as well as his or her capability to express thoughts more effectively (Hyland & Hyland, 2006). That said, there is a conspicuous void in literature concerning the most viable approaches for teaching ESL learners in Lebanon. This gap was filled by this study through examining the root of coherence problems in student writing with a view to recommending appropriate measures to overcome them. The results further informed educational policy formulation through designing evidence-informed approaches to improving learners' writing coherence in ESL classrooms.

1.6 Purpose of the Study

The current study examined how AI writing tools could help improve cohesion in writing among grade 7 and 8 learners of a Lebanese private school. The learners at this level have always struggled with cohesion, which is vital for the smoothness and clarity of their written work. This research utilized qualitative methods such as interviews and focus groups conducted on the learners and teachers, respectively, to get into their worlds regarding challenges of cohesion and the strategies currently used. This study sought to examine the factors behind these problems through a qualitative investigation. It sought to understand how teachers of grade 7 and 8 foster coherence among their learners. Moreover, it focused on their active didactic processes in

teaching the subject matter. Moreover, it analyzed the degree to which artificial intelligence (AI) tools enhance coherence. The study, therefore, undertook qualitative evaluation for the purposes of increasing learners' writing coherence and academic achievement through the blending of conventional teaching approaches with AI-assisted teaching. The researcher sought the assistance of many educators, including group members and other participants, on coping strategies for enhancing writing for analogous educational contexts.

1.7 Research Questions

Research Question 1: How do teachers and learners of grades 7 and 8 perceive the challenges of writing cohesion in a private Lebanese school?

Research Question 2: To what extent do AI writing tools improve writing cohesion among grade 7 and 8 learners in a private Lebanese school compared to conventional methods?

1.8 Research Expectations

This study was supported by the research expectations listed below:

Expectation 1: Both learners and teachers will pinpoint particular difficulties regarding achieving writing cohesion, emphasizing the gap between grammar focus and logical flow of ideas.

Expectation 2: AI writing tools will aid learners in employing cohesive devices and organizing their ideas logically and hierarchically in a manner conducive to flow.

Expectation 3: The perception learners have regarding writing, as well their engagement with the revision process, will be more positive with the integration of AI-powered feedback tools into the instruction process.

Expectation 4: Instructional designers will appreciate AI writing tools for their role as a complementary resource within a structured instructional framework, rather than viewing them as a replacement for teacher intervention.

1.9 Significance of the Study

This investigation helped close the gap in existing literature concerning the teaching of writing for Lebanese private high school learners by reviewing their particular problem with cohesion (Astari, 2021). It integrated the perspective offered by the learners and their teachers about cohesion so that their conceptions and misconceptions can be useful in formulating instructional designs that attend to the learners' needs. Improving teaching practice and constructing professional development opportunities aimed at helping teachers teach for writing cohesion require these insights (Harris et al., 2012).

In addition, this study focused on how AI writing tools can assist in overcoming some of the challenges identified. They offered AI technology solutions that improve writing cohesion by providing ESL learners with appropriate feedback and guidance (Graham & Perin, 2007). The results showed gaps that AI writing tools fulfill in the difficulties created by the traditional approach to writing instruction sorely needed and which could not be remedied by simple methodologies.

This form of analysis aided instructors in creating techniques to integrate AI into composition classes. Learning the ways in which AI aids learners helped educators modify instructional strategies to better assist learners in their learning activities and writing processes. This resulted in more instructional design and care that fosters motivation and productivity which enhanced the learners' achievement (Dias & Agata, 2013).

On a wider scope, the research was relevant for curriculum designers and policy makers interested in the infusion of AI in national and school-based educational systems. This research helped support technology-based literacy and writing skills interventions to address cohesion problems and therefore, justified the integration of AI technology (Crossley & McNamara, 2016). Furthermore, the qualitative method of this study contributed to the body of literature on the impact of AI writing tools on the development of writing skills in different ages and educational stages for many years to come.

This research comprehensively addressed issues related to cohesion in student writing and explored how AI can contribute to resolving these challenges. It achieved this by aligning instructional processes with student needs, integrating effective teaching approaches, and leveraging the advantages of AI technology.

1.10 Limitations and Delimitations

Every research has specific set boundaries within which it is required to function and so distinct limitations. There are two categories of constraints, namely limitations and delimitations.

Limitations concern the uncontrollable, imposed constraints affecting the accuracy, scope, and generalizability of the study, which includes sample size, time, and even technology. Conversely, delimitation is defined as the boundary that the researcher sets, which includes population,

methods, location, etc. The researcher focused on the kind of study that investigates how AI writing tools can enhance the writing cohesion skills of learners in grades 7 and 8, and have purposely set up some delimitations and limitations. It was vital to know these aspects while attempting to draw appropriate conclusions from the answer to the question.

Limitations of the Study

Even though it offered insightful information on how AI writing tools can enhance writing cohesion in grade 7 and 8 learners, few factors must be taken into account while analyzing the results. In this matter, these limitations reduce neither the importance nor the value of the results; instead, they emphasize further investigation or studies in order to broaden the comprehension of the subject matter.

Range of Sample Size and Generalization: The research was confined to one private institution located in Beirut, Lebanon. The learners and teaching methods suffered from homogenization and were not representative of the diversity of other schools, particularly public ones or those located in different regions of Lebanon. Therefore, the findings cannot be assumed phenomena in the other Lebanese private schools or the international contexts without further proof.

Target Audience: The study sought out 7th and 8th graders who are starting to engage in sophisticated writing tasks. This focus enabled a thorough examination of the writing cohesion problems this age group faces. However, the older and younger learners may not fit the same patterns, which other grades as younger learners or older learners might not. Subsequent research could look at AI's impact on cohesion in writing across different developmental levels to better understand their influence.

Lack of Time: The study did not incorporate AI writing tools affecting longitudinal analysis within its temporal boundaries. The research has concentrated on AI implementation effects on the learners' writing cohesion over an abbreviated period. These impacts were observed within the span of a few months, which means there is no information about the perpetuity of the improvements or the changes in the improvements over time as learners continue using AI writing tools.

Self-Reported Data: Teachers and learners provided information in focus groups and interviews, which was, from their perspective, self-reported. While this narrative approach was beneficial in providing rich qualitative accounts of perceptions and experiences, it is necessary to consider the biases that might arise from self-reporting. Answers would have been provided from a viewpoint which is socially favorable, or were not fully explained, hence the data reliability and authenticity is questionable.

Technological Limitations: The effectiveness of AI writing tools implemented in this study was somewhat dependent on the performance of the technology. Certain times there were some issues with the software, which resulted in problems like poor quality feedback, and other issues that were unpredictable. These issues may have reduced the impact of the tools and created new unwanted factors that were not considered in the beginning of the research.

Delimitations of the Study

The researcher particularly designed the study with certain boundaries to provide useful information and insights while focusing on a context. These boundaries aid in defining the scope of the research where the findings are limited.

Geographic Focus: The study was limited to a private school in Beirut. This deliberate focus

provides a good understanding of the implementation of AI writing tools in a specific school. On the other hand, the results cannot be generalized to other schools, especially those in different regions with distinct educational systems or levels of technology. Moreover, the study does not consider how the AI writing tools would work in other countries or in poor public schools with alternative teacher allocation methods.

Student Population: The research focused on 7th and 8th graders who were studying English as a second language. Although this narrowed scope helped analyze the writing cohesion issue in ESL pupils, it excluded others, such as the younger children and native speakers. There is room for future able learners that are more senior and other non-English language learning populations.

AI Writing Tools' Selection: The influence of AI instruments meant for grammar checking and coherence analysis cohesion was analyzed. Although they created an advancement in the application of AI for educational purposes, the research neglected the rest of the AI forms, devices centered on vocabulary, and reading comprehension. Thus, the results are limited to the impact of AI on cohesion in writing within the frame of teaching composition.

Research Design: The researcher designed the research under a qualitative methodology, emphasizing focus group discussions and interviews as the main sources of data from participants, in this case learners and teachers. This approach was selected to obtain deeper and more personal information about participants' views on cohesion in writing and the role of AI technology. Nevertheless, the absence of quantitative evidence renders this study incapable of justifying claims about the effectiveness of AI instruments. The research is based on their perceptions without measurable indicators, which may affect the comprehensiveness of the

findings.

Scope and Limitations: The study was conducted within one academic year, which constrained the consideration of the AI writing tools impacts to only the short term. It focused on the immediate impacts on learners' writing cohesion without consideration of the possibility of considerable improvement over time or the AI-induced benefits lasting over time. In order to comprehend the prolonging impact of AI writing tools, an extended study would have to be conducted.

1.11 Assumptions of the Study

As in any research study, certain fundamental assumptions need to be made for defining the scope in which data is to be collected, analyzed, and interpreted. Defining assumptions is crucial since it determines the scope within which the study was going to be carried out and what is expected in terms of participants, tools, and methods. In this study that focused on the integration of AI writing tools in promoting writing cohesion in grade 7 and 8 learners, there were a number of assumptions that needed to be made. Such assumptions related to effectiveness of AI learning, willingness of participants, performance of the technology, and credibility of the qualitative analysis. All of these assumptions had boundaries that helped conduct the research and at the same time indicate gaps for future research.

AI Writing Tools Improve Cohesion in Writing: The study was based on the assumption that AI Writing tools meant for grammar checking and coherence analysis assist learners in improving their writing cohesion. It assumed that there were tools that assist learners so that they could make improvements and edits which made their writing more fluid and well organized.

Further, it assumed that the AI-produced feedback was credible and conformed to the principles of generic writing logic, rationale, and order.

Respondent's Comments Will Be True To the Best of Their Knowledge: Learners and teachers in the AI-assisted writing focus groups and interviews were, for the purposes of this study, willing to share their real experiences and perceptions, thus making the assumption. It was possible to have self-reported outcomes that had social acceptability bias, but it was assumed that the participants did not overstate or understate claims. This assumption was one of the supporting pillars that led to formation of qualitative conclusions during the research.

Learners Followed Directions in Using the AI Writing Tools: It was assumed that learners used the AI writing tools willingly and regularly in their writing practice. This implied that they complied with the directions given which included how to use the tools and the received feedback, and those they did not avoid using the technology on purpose. Any differences in engagement levels across subjects was believed to be low and did not have a substantial impact on the study outcome.

AI Writing Tools Worked Properly: With some slight tech limitations, it was believed that the AI writing tools integrated into the study accurately operated as expected by grammar correcting, providing cohesion, and enhancing the writing. The study argued that any bugs or errors in the AI software design did not have a significant effect on how the learners learned. Furthermore, it assumed that learners and teachers paraphrased and interpreted the AI provided feedback appropriately.

Writing Cohesion was a Subjective Evaluation: Kreth and Neumann's study, which relied on focus group discussions and interviews instead of quantifying metrics, accepts that qualitative assessments of writing cohesion, along with its cohesive relations, are accurate and trustworthy. That means, from this standpoint, instructors and learners subjects are knowledgeable and experienced enough to interpret and make judgments regarding the alterations of cohesion through changes over time. This assumption suggested that instructors and learners had the competence to assess and express how there was an alteration in the writing coherence pertaining to their usage and reading of some text samples. While some measurable indicators of linguistic complexity scores provided insight, the study claimed qualitative processes unarguably influence outcomes.

Results were Within the Given Context: The study posited the results were valid within the scope of the private school teaching context located in Beirut, Lebanon. Though every school comes with its set of pedagogical approaches and technologies available, there lies hope that the results provided valuable insight concerning the advantages and challenges of AI-supported teaching resources for writing. Regardless, these conclusions would require additional research prior to being applied to other schools or international contexts.

Potential Long Term Trends Indicated by Short Term Changes: Though the study covered a short span of time, it attempted to explain the observed improvements in learners' writing cohesion as possible long-term gains. The belief was that learners who made use of AI writing tools in writing during the research period would be able to maintain those skills and possibly improve them over time. The gap, however, was that this study cannot have definite conclusions about the impact without a longitudinal design.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Cohesion within a piece of writing refers to, ‘the mechanical and linguistic techniques that integrate elements and guarantee the proper logical order of a text’ (Crossley & McNamara, 2016). Learners in junior high school, mainly in eighth and ninth grades, easily grasp cohesion, which is the more complex form of writing to construct compared to simple structures (Anderson et al., 2023). Well-organized texts allow readers to track the logic of ideas being presented, as such, making reading easy and comprehension better (Allen et al., 2021). Sadly, many learners at this age seem to struggle with cohesion, as they do not know how to use cohesive devices such as conjunctions, transitions, pronouns, and lexical ties appropriately (Astari, 2021).

In particular, transitions and conjunctions serve to relate ideas that drive the reader progressively through an argument or story (Alharbi & Alqefari, 2021).

The technology that we have today has made it possible to create AI (Artificial Intelligence) technologies that can help learners master different aspects of writing, including cohesion (Abdul Rahman et al., 2022). They can enhance the quality of writing by improving its clarity and coherence, and writing quality feedback helps in providing real-time suggestions (Abdalkader, 2022). AI writing tools, such as automated writing evaluation systems, have proven to be helpful in assisting children to improve their writing skills through focused feedback and adaptive teaching approaches (Brusilovsky & Millán, 2007). The changing of schools to AI use gives learners more help in performing cohesive writing tasks that could greatly transform their approach to dealing with writing assignments (Bhutoria, 2022).

Considering how fast AI is advancing in the field of education, there is a clear importance in evaluating the impact it has in helping learners be more proficient over time (Cahyono et al., 2023).

2.2 Purpose of the Review

This chapter reviewed existing literature regarding the use of AI technology to improve writing cohesion at a private school in Lebanon for 7th and 8th graders. It aimed to understand the solutions learners try to achieve cohesion, analyze the efficacy of AI writing tools in accomplishing these objectives, and study how AI-assisted procedures are different from non-AI assisted approaches to teaching cohesion.

Cohesion is the logical ordering and linking of ideas in writing, and its specific devices include conjunctions, transitions, and pronouns (Kaur, 2018). These devices help connect sentences, paragraphs, and other sections of a text, which helps understanding. Unfortunately, a number of middle school learners find it very difficult to achieve writing cohesion as they progress to higher levels of academic work. Given the importance of communication skills, researchers have made numerous attempts—especially those focused on artificial intelligence—to help learners master this enabling skill.

The researcher constructed the review using the following main overarching themes: (1) issues of writing cohesion, (2) educational AI writing tools, (3) teaching writing in an AI-generated context, and (4) assessment of AI and traditional approaches for teaching cohesion.

This review takes an empirical, theoretical, and critique based approach to analyze the gaps of existing research and the evolution of theoretical models and frameworks relevant to AI's potential in writing pedagogy. The scope of this review was limited to the last ten years, which

makes data related to the discussion more pertinent and up-to-date in regards to novel AI writing tools and teaching methods.

After analyzing the impacts and relations of AI-powered writing tools, this review attempts to bridge the gap in existing research regarding AI education on the cohesive and comparative aspects of writing versus traditional teaching methodologies. Knowledge of the influence AI exerts on teaching writing is critical, especially in a time where technology is changing the education paradigm.

AI Writing Tools in ESL Contexts: Improving Cohesiveness of a Text

The use of AI in education is ever growing, especially in preparing English as a Second Language (ESL) learners' writing. Recent publications address how AI writing tools intend to enhance cohesion in student writing. This is because learners' written work is aided by getting comments on grammar, coherence, and cohesion in real time.

Grammarly , ProWriting Aid , Turnitin, and Writerly are known among the ESL learners in regards to grammar and coherence problems. These programs help to detect grammar mistakes, provide suggestions on sentence arrangement, and comment on coherence and cohesion. As an illustration, Grammarly helps to improve sentence structure in a way that learners use cohesive devices (conjunctions, reference words) appropriately. Pro Writing Aid helps learners with their flow and transitions between paragraphs so that logical relations among ideas are preserved.

Writerly is one of the AI writing tools that has gained attention because of its real-time feedback feature that helps improve cohesion in writing. Unlike other tools that aid in correcting grammatical errors or general stylistic refinements, Writerly aids learners in enhancing cohesion by offering suggestions in relation to transitions, connections of sentences, and organization of

the texts. This capability makes Writerly useful to ESL learners who face challenges in logically sequencing their ideas or linking concepts in a coherent manner.

Additionally, tools powered by AI such as QuillBot help learners with sentence and passage paraphrasing, which greatly improves writing coherence. It has been established that this type of AI tool can enable ESL learners to identify cohesion problems, such as reference words, sentence connectors and logical order, in need of intervention (Xie et al., 2022). This enables ESL learners to interact with their writing, receive instant feedback, and revise in relation to the comments made, which results in the development of cohesive and coherent texts.

Chen and Xie's (2022) investigated the resources and tools integrated with artificial intelligence, particularly their impact on cohesive essay writing AI technology was estimated to have contributed to the enhanced grammatical accuracy and coherence in the essays of the ESL learners; therefore, they were able to “better” accomplish “multi-paragraph” essays. Moreover, Dai et al. (2023) illustrate how AI programs helped ESL learners correct cohesion problems in their drafts to improve their final compositions. ESL learners face many challenges, one being chain of thought cohesion, and this work helped to fill the gap.

With the increased integration of AI in writing instructions, this research narrows down to the use of the Writerly AI writing tool specifically designed to enhance cohesion for ESL learners. This research aims to understand the effectiveness of AI engagement in writing. It is done by observing how Writerly helps ESL learners structure their ideas with cohesive devices and logical progression.

AI Writing Tools for seventh and eighth Graders - Writing Cohesion

The use of Artificial Intelligence tools for writing cohesion for middle school learners especially

the 7th and 8th graders is an emerging area of study. At this stage, learners are starting to learn more advanced writing techniques and this could be the best time to introduce AI powered writing tools. The tools can enhance learners' work with the help of feedback, self-evaluation and instant responses for writing cohesion achievement that are essential for writing cohesion advancement.

Research regarding the use of AI writing tools and the writing cohesion specifically for learners of grades 7 and 8 is absent, but there are existing studies with the same age range that can help. Kim (2022), for instance, noted that upper elementary and early middle school learners were able to improve their writing cohesion with the use of AI powered tools like Google docs and Writerly, which provided the learners with feedback about the coherence of their writing in real time. This helped the learners to improve the use of cohesive devices and logical sequencing. More specifically, the personalized suggestions offered by these tools are geared towards helping learners understand and address cohesion errors, such as missing or improperly used transition phrases or poorly structured paragraphs. The feedback provided enables learners to enhance the organization of their ideas and the logical progression between them, which enhances the overall coherence of their writing.

Conventional Methods for Teaching Writing Cohesion

Even though AI technology offers new approaches to improve cohesion in writing, the traditional methods teachers use to help learners produce cohesive body texts still matters. Traditional approaches have always given attention to the logical structure of a student's writing and effective use of cohesive devices.

Teaching cohesion traditionally is predominantly done with the following methods:

Direct Teaching of Cohesion Devices. Instructing learners on the use of cohesive devices such as conjunctions, reference phrases (he, this), and transitional words (on the other hand, in addition). These lessons aim to teach learners the connections that need to be made between sentences and paragraphs for the smooth flow of ideas.

Structuring and Topic Mapping: Outlines are one of the widely used strategies in teaching writing cohesion. Teachers guide learners in drafting essays by clustering their main ideas and supporting details logically prior to writing; this way, learners are able to logically organize their writing, and thus enhance cohesiveness.

Collaborative Writing and Peer Review: The traditional classrooms have utilized peer review sessions as an efficient way of enhancing learners' writing cohesion. Learners are able to analyze one another's work during peer review sessions and offer insights on where there is need for improvement, for instance, transitions between paragraphs and arguments. In addition, this helps learners to work together and improve their writing skills socially (Vygotsky, 1978).

Implementation of Feedback: Teachers still offer their learners written comments and respond to feedback using the same method outlining linkages that need to be improved. Such feedback often suggests alterations to a sentence and provides additional phrases along with changes to the order of paragraphs to assist the flow of ideas.

Dialogue/Discussion: Arguments may be refined further in a conversation that allows for questioning called the Socratic Method.

In terms of other conventional approaches, the teaching of cohesion strategies, peer review, and

instructor feedback are techniques known to improve learners' writing cohesion skills. For instance, learners were able to write well-structured and coherent essays when they were taught specific writing strategies, including monitoring and using cohesive devices, as noted by Graham & Perin (2007). In addition, Luo & Hyland (2021) reported learners could identify and solve cohesion issues because of the feedback received during peer review and from the instructor. However, AI technologies are simple to use and increase productivity, their real value is apparent when combined with conventional teaching methods. Learners tend to achieve the greatest improvement in writing with coherence at the integration of AI feedback, teacher intervention, and collaborative peer work.

Studies on the Effectiveness of Conventional Methods

An extensive amount of documents has analyzed the effectiveness of cohesion teaching with orthodox methods. For instance, Graham and Perin (2007) showed that teaching explicitly about cohesion, including the teaching of cohesive devices and logical ordering, greatly enhanced learners' ability to write coherent essays. Also, Luo and Hyland (2021) reported that peer review and student-teacher evaluation greatly assisted learners in resolving problems of cohesion within their texts and thus raised the quality of their writing.

Moreover, several such studies, including Lebanese ones, have investigated these methods. For instance, Aljaafil and Beyhan (2023) studied the perceptions of English language pedagogy held by participants purportedly teaching English to grade 12 pupils in public schools in Lebanon. The study identified serious misalignment between the curriculum and student's writing capabilities which exposed that explicit teaching of cohesive devices was needed in their instructional practice to enhance coherence in pupils' writing. This is one more evidence about

the importance of orthodox methodology enhanced with modern technology tools in the classroom (Aljaafil & Beyhan, 2023).

Moreover, Bacha (2002) investigated problems ESL learners faced in writing within the context of Lebanon. The research highlighted difficulties learners encounter with cohesion and coherence in their writing. The study noted that some instructional approaches might not be overly helpful in resolving these problems; additional aid through cohesive devices instruction may be required to facilitate such writing. This shows more the skepticism of traditional approaches, especially those that are modified to counter the growing sophistication of learners in Lebanon (Bacha, 2002).

2.3 Comparative Evaluation of Conventional Methods vs. AI Writing Tools

The efficiency of peer review, teacher feedback, and direct teaching of cohesive devices integration still comprises an important instructional strategy in modern education. Nonetheless, they tend to consume more time and do not provide the same level of immediacy of feedback workload as artificial intelligence technologies do when compared to conventional techniques. AI writing tools, such as Writerly, provide instantaneous feedback on cohesion problems, as learners are able to revise their writing while it is in progress.

Although traditional tools may still be as effective, they seem to center pedagogical dependency and availability, as they do not generate immediate or personalized feedback as AI writing tools do. Additionally, while constructive peer review and collaborative techniques are beneficial, they often hinder learners' capacity to critique, or even identify their peers' work. On the other hand, AI writing tools conduct a more sophisticated analysis on writing, and offer suggestions on

cohesion that do not require the presence of a teacher or peers.

The use of both AI writing tools and traditional methods tend to provide the best results in improving writing cohesion. Issues of cohesion can be fixed in real time with AI writing tools, while traditional methods, like teacher and peer feedback, encourage greater interaction with the text and its reasoning. Combining the use of AI writing tools with traditional teaching methods gives learners the best possible approach to AI-centered writing pedagogy.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

To understand better how AI writing tools affect narrative integration of 7th and 8th grader learners sequentially and cumulatively, it is important to oppose the socio-cultural theory of cognitive constructivism. In both these theories, learners are an active actor, the aim for them is to acquire the knowledge, but the knowledge acquired is through the social context embedded within them, in which the learners are active with the learning.

On the other hand, Cognitive Constructivism stresses the role of AI writing tools in expanding gaps that learners possess. Writing is a cognitive action, and for learners to be able to express coherent writing structure, coherence construction must take place, to which learners have the ability as Piaget stressed. This highlights the impact of experience on student learning. Learners are able to assimilate AI writing tools into their writing processes to improve the overall output. The nature of writing itself with the iterative factors such as drafting, feedback aim at the same goal – coherence construction. Writing assignments generally reinforce goal-orientated practice that comes naturally with the formation of reflective activities that match the goals required, enabling student writers to free form and directly experience cohesive writing.

As Vygotsky pointed out, social interactions and cultural context are vital in learning. This means that social and cultural contexts are important in enhancing understanding. This is because there are tools such as language, technology, and others that are used to learn. In classrooms, learners come together to write and edit each other's work. AI writing tools are examples of tools that help with such tasks. When learners come together in such groups, they can engage in discussions that promote their understanding of coherence and cohesion and through that, they can scaffold around effective writing practices.

In order to broaden the framework, it makes sense to look at other frameworks that are consistent with the goals of the study. The following theories provide some explain how writing becomes more cohesive when AI writing tools are employed during the writing process:

Activity Theory

Activity Theory focuses on the relationship between people, artifacts, and their environments in a learning situation (Kaptelinin & Nardi, 2012). In this view, learning is said to take place through mediated actions and tools are salient. In the case of this research, AI writing tools can be seen as such mediators. With these tools, learners can practice and improve their collaborative writing strategies and have a better understanding of cohesion as they constantly negotiate and work through meaning and flow within their texts. Since Activity Theory emphasizes the collaborative and social aspects of learning it provides a useful perspective to examine the role of AI writing tools in the creation of coherent texts.

Social Cognitive Theory

This social cognitive theory encompasses social learning and cognitive development and focuses on the learning outcome of the individual within the social context (Schunk, 2016). This theory in particular is useful when exploring how learners acquire the writing strategies with interdependence on the other learners and teachers when making use of AI. For instance, AI writing aids that encourage peer review and joint editing help the learners to improve their grasp of coherence and cohesion in writing. In the process of social learning, children see and do effective writing and hence their writing improves with practice.

Constructivism Learning Theory

This one asserts that learners build the understanding as they engage in practice and reflect on their practice (Brusilovsky & Millán, 2007). Within the scenario of AI writing tools in use, the learners are able to create meaning in writing, as constructivists would advocate for. The process of drafting and revising that is made possible by the use of AI writing tools helps learners to think critically about their writing, more specifically, about the relationship between cohesive devices and the effectiveness of communication. Using the AI devices, the learners are able to learn to appreciate the contribution of cohesive devices to their written output quality.

In conclusion, this structure is comprehensive in explaining how AI writing devices affect learners' writing interconnectedness by bringing together cognitive constructivism and sociocultural theory with Activity Theory, Social Cognitive Theory, and Constructivist Learning Theory. All these theories, we have gone through, underscore the need for active participation, socialization, and the use of contextual factors in learning. The theoretical insights that emerge

from this framework briefly will also engender the specific research design and the analysis of data collected and allow for the detailed examination of how AI writing tools can help improve learners' writing skills and unified communication.

Theoretical framework diagram: Bantalem Derseh Wale & Yirgalem Fentie Kassahun - First published: 01 April 2024

2.5 Review of Related Literature

Cognitive Constructivism and AI Writing Technologies

cognitive constructivism. Piaget's cognitive constructivism is based on the idea that children make their own knowledge of phenomena by the way of activity and reflection after (Powell & Kalina, 2009). As a result, it deals with how people form their mental structures in the process of learning; this is important for understanding how AI can be used to facilitate learning through iterative feedback, which improves these mental structures(Chugh et al., 2023).

Cognitive constructivism is relevant when discussing AI writing tools because these tools enable learners to actively participate in improving their writing through interactive ways (Powell & Kalina , 2009). Learners are able to create a more sophisticated comprehension of writing mechanics and styles by using such mechanisms as real-time correction and suggestion with subsequent revision (Alabdulkarim, 2021). This cyclic method meets the principles of constructivism through which learners can make use of the tool to build up and rebuild knowledge.

Sociocultural Theory and the Role of AI Writing Tools

sociocultural. The idea of sociocultural theory in Vygotsky highlights the connection between cognitive development and social interaction as well as cultural tools. The principal concepts are Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) which is the range of tasks learners can do with assistance but cannot yet do alone and Scaffolding that involves support in order for learners to accomplish tasks within their ZPDs (De Costa, 2007).

Digital scaffolds are like artificial intelligence writing tools that provide specific information and support within a student's ZPD. They suggest or correct in order to help learners finish challenging writing tasks they could not do alone. This backing enhances skills of writing and understanding; therefore, it aligns with sociocultural theory that emphasizes on assistance and involvement during learning (Anderson et al., 2023).

Integration of Theoretical Frameworks in Previous Research

In the digital learning tools landscape, researchers have shown that cognitive constructivism as well as sociocultural theory can be applied. One such example is the study conducted by Huang et al. (2023) who found out that writing skills are improved with AI writing tools through giving feedback on principles of writing that learners can understand and apply repeatedly in line with cognitive constructivism. Furthermore, Puntambekar (2021) also demonstrated how these same artificial intelligence systems provide scaffolding within ZPDs for learners according to socio-cultural theories.

These pieces of research indicate that there is an agreement between practical applications backed by theoretical frameworks to better educational outcomes. This means that AI should give more than one iteration's worth of feedback because it helps with cognitive growth since it assists children in refining their written language abilities thereby acting like a scaffold towards understanding different concepts (Dai et al., 2023). This correlation supports the idea that cohesion in writing can be improved through use of AI writing tools.

Application of Theoretical Framework to Current Study

Cognitive constructivism and sociocultural theory serve as the foundation for this research, which seeks to examine how AI writing tools affect cohesion in writing. According to cognitive

constructivism, which has been described by modern scholars like Chen et al. (2022), learning is an active process that involves learners' construction on their existing knowledge through experience. This model illuminates the way in which these programs can help learners actively participate with their writing through iterative feedback and improve skillfulness.

Sociocultural theory, on the other hand, is rooted in the work of Vygotsky. It emphasizes social interaction and scaffolding as crucial elements in cognitive development (Poehner et al., 2018). It suggests that digital scaffolds such as AI writing tools should be used within a student's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) so that they may provide specific guidance for improvement based on where a learner currently stands. Currently there are studies showing that recent investigations into this kind of tutoring have shown that it provides support for learners who need it most while still considering what each individual student can do at any given time – an example being adaptive contextualized support according to abilities identified by Kim (2022) during the writing process.

By using both of these theories together, we hope to find out more about how different types or categories of knowledge may be built up around writing when certain activities take place with AI writing tools acting as mediators between them so they fall within ZPDs levels suitable for learners at different stages of development. The paper also seeks to find out more about how much scaffolding is required for learners to be able to attain higher levels of success in academic writing tasks. Such considerations will be useful when designing educational strategies aimed at improving cohesion among learners' texts using artificial intelligence along the lines proposed by Dai et al. (2023) or other researchers who have engaged themselves into similar inquiries before now – all references should be given.

A Glimpse of AI Usage in the Educational Environment: Scope and Limitations

Nowadays, the concept of artificial intelligence tools can be seen as being fully embedded within the ordinary educational activities across all the levels of education as a way of assisting learners in their writing by providing comments on grammar, coherence and sentences. Other investigations corroborate the benefits of AI integration in learning and core competencies acquisition, most especially, in the case of essay writing where ESL learners stand to gain the most (Astari, 2021). At this stage, for instance, Astari (2021) reported AI writing tools as being able to assist learners in detecting and correcting grammatical errors and cohesive devices in a sentence for ease of better communication.

Nonetheless, newer research has shed light on significant obstacles faced when deploying AI for composition, especially when discussing uses such as critical focus, creativity or cultural and contextual support. Xu and Wang (2023) argue that, while AI performs well in basic forms of negative feedback, it cannot manage more complex writing tasks, including reasoning, tone, and audience targeting. These limitations are attributed to AIs being programmed to perform set tasks and as such cannot react to different linguistic and cultural environments which are important in multilingual classrooms especially ESL learners (Xu & Wang, 2023).

Additionally, student involvement issues while employing AI writing tools have also been brought up by Yin (2022). In the case of learners who abuse AI writing tools in this manner (using it to make corrections of their written work), an alarming truth may occur wherein such learners do not engage in learning but rather rely on systems feedback to make the necessary changes. This kind of dependence is likely to erode the voluntary act of critical thinking in the sense that learners may skip the pre-requisites of self-analysis and self-critique that are needed

for one to become a competent writer. Yin's observations are consistent with previous studies that demonstrate that AI-mediated feedback, although fast, detracts from engagement in writing processes that are more complex and exploratory, such as developing and structuring ideas and arguments (Yin, 2022).

These opposing viewpoints indicate the necessity of an effective balance of AI writing tools in writing instructions and an active teacher's role. Graham and Perin (2007) explain that advanced writing teaching normally includes making learners think deeper by providing them with guidance, addressing their feedback, and being engaged in the process of writing instruction, which cannot be done using AI writing tools alone. As mentioned above, AI can provide assistance where mundane feedback is a need; however, its application should aim to be embedded within a broader context of a pedagogical situation that is still interactive whereby teachers assist learners in more cognitively demanding and situational contexts (Graham & Perin, 2007).

2.6 Thematic Overview

Identifying and interpreting important themes from the data is critical when conducting research on the impacts of AI writing instruments on pupils' writing cohesion. These themes augment understanding on the ways these tools influence various aspects of writing and education. Our goal in looking at these themes is to understand better what exactly AI does regarding improving coherence and effectiveness in written work. This thematic analysis seeks out hidden patterns or trends that indicate both strengths and weaknesses related to artificial intelligence (AI) writing instruments used for education purposes. Such an evaluation would assist us in knowing their

overall influence on learners' achievements while pointing out areas where they can be perfected further.

The most important themes we found during our research are: (1) writing cohesion challenges; (2) AI writing tools in the educational context ;(3) teaching writing in the artificial intelligence era. The researcher will examine each theme thoroughly with respect to its relevance towards answering research questions posed, thereby giving a complete picture about findings reached by this study.

Writing Cohesion Challenges

According to Kern (2008), writing is a vital tool in academic language learning because writing enables learners to think explicitly about how to arrange and communicate their thoughts, feelings or ideas with respect to the anticipated readers. Writing is nothing but just writing as seen from that statement above but its goal is to develop ideas for communication especially with the reader and thus language comes out as text (Thornbury, 2017). It means that learners in higher levels of education must be able to write academic papers first because they have to submit research findings on specific subjects as an exit requirement for their graduation.

Secondly, since almost all fields of career will require writing skill in future life so there is a need for it generally. Similarly, Nurlia (2021) agrees with Kern (2008) when he argues that writing is about thinking through ideas, expressing them verbally and putting them into sentences and paragraphs that are meaningful and clear for readers. In other words, the definition stated above implies that writing expresses the organized thoughts leading into statements or

paragraphs as well. Of these ideas, none is more important than being able to turn them into sentences or even paragraphs, though it is often the hardest thing to do by many learners.

Chadafi (2023) supports this idea which presents an argument that learners' problem while they are writing doesn't just come up with organizing the ideas but also putting these words together in a way that can be understood by someone else reading his work. It should be noted that a readable text has coherence i.e., if its sentences hang together making sense (it's cohesive).

However, cohesion in a given text may appear at face value if the developed ideas are not related; then it does not make any sense at all. To achieve interaction between the reader and the text therefore involves use of cohesive devices, which makes it easy for one person to read and understand the text (Thornbury 2017). Another writer who supports this argument is Okoth (2015); according to him, coherence of a text is related to the situation or culture that are interconnected. Coherence, in his opinion, is how everything fits together well and it does not exist in words or structures but people.

Furthermore, Saiful (2019) claims there are complex elements of writing that include content, organizing, originality, style, fluency, accuracy or rhetorical forms of discourse and thus writers should identify the most important ones that have to be considered during writing. Leonard (2019) says that language needs prioritizing developing ideas since it represents experiences that we go through daily. Johnson et al. (2003) refers to such statements as thesis statements and topic sentences. Paragraphs are different in structure and a topic sentence may be placed at the end, at the beginning, in the middle of paragraph or even in both the opening and closing lines. Generally, it is just after placing the main idea at the onset of a paragraph that there ensues

development of some or more details. These details are examples or statements that may assist readers understand fully what the main idea is about.

However, this task is not easy, as it requires experience gained from reading various books, articles that influence greatly on how ideas should be developed by any writer intending to come up with an essay. As much as one may think that simply putting words together forms sentences that form paragraphs, writing meaningfully connected sentences within a composition is difficult for most under-graduate learners who regularly use simple sentences. In order to link related ideas within one paragraph, academic writing demands that learners write long sentences though. Nyoman (2018) defines the ‘content’ of learners’ performance as the measures of their correct utterances about the specified tasks. “Organization and cohesion” refers to the overall layout, clarity, and flow of the points presented. The measure of the vocabulary that is used is called ‘range’. A check of ‘register’ is a check on the level of the style in relation to the topic, text type, purpose, and audience. ‘Target reader’ refers to the user of the language and their potential understanding. According to Thornbury (2017), initially the content is evaluated in particular by the Cambridge Advanced English Examination criteria, followed by organization and cohesion, and afterwards other areas of concern such as register, target reader, language accuracy, and range.

The content refers to how well the assigned topic was addressed; organization and cohesion refer to the orderliness of ideas as expressed in the text; range means whether or not there is sufficient wide range of vocabulary and grammatical structures; register means choosing a style suitable for the topic, the type of text, purpose and target reader. On the other hand, the target reader is concerned about addressing his mind towards this problem, whereas accuracy of language is

thought to be seen through if it is coherent in its using lexis or morphology etc. (Thornbury 2017). For example, El-Dali (2011) states that inaccurate production may involve sentences which are produced accurately but contain many mistakes such as wrong verb forms or articles omitted errors. According to Llach (2011), accuracy is referred to as exactness, precision and fitness of transmitted information .

The theme of writing cohesion problems is all encompassing , touching on various issues concerning writing cohesion such as its importance in academic and professional contexts as well as challenges learners face when generating and organizing ideas. It utilizes insights from a number of scholars such as Thornbury, Kern, and El-Dali thus giving a rounded perspective of the topic. In addition to this, it provides precise definitions for cohesion coherence and accuracy which guarantees a common understanding among all. Furthermore, it emphasizes issues such as the placement of topic sentences and the practical evaluation of student writing.

Despite this, the subject does not imply some specific strategies in which these challenges can be solved. Different pedagogical techniques and tools such as the usage of artificial intelligence (AI) essay generators are necessary to improve writing among learners but this demands further research. Fourth, failure to include different types of learners, especially those with different levels of language proficiency who may come up against separate challenges calling for individual aid. Nevertheless it would have been better if this had been discussed in terms of strong points and areas that needed more study thereby leading to a more balanced and comprehensive analysis.

AI Writing Tools in the Educational Context

The use of artificial intelligence and technology in different areas of education has been increasingly widespread, particularly affecting learners' writing. In a survey conducted by Kurniati & Fithriani (2022), it was demonstrated that applying QuillBot is helpful for learners to improve paraphrasing skills, which are critical to academic writing (Thangthong et al., 2024). Researchers found that these tools could actually enable scientists to write with more perfection, quickness as well as accuracy thus allowing them to concentrate on their main research activities (Xu et al., 2023).

Nonetheless, we should also recognize the difficulties and disadvantages of using AI in scientific writing. Thus, by utilizing electronic devices with artificial intelligence for teachers, they bring out the best from learners. This means how lecturers teach and how learners learn may change due to interaction between technology and pedagogy. In this process artificial intelligence, technology is integrated for smoothing the learning process, (Haysim et al., 2023). Storey (2023) recently identified some of the challenges experienced by EFL doctoral candidates including issues of mechanical errors in writing mechanics as well as argument coherence along with dissertation structure. This study stressed on copy editing as well as proofreading for addressing mechanics and building logical arguments respectively. Using formal language, transitional sentences for text cohesion, citations for claims support, and maintaining consistent dissertation structure were stressed too.

Moreover, Kurniati & Fithriani (2022) explored post-graduate learners' perceptions about Quillbot where a positive response was indicated. Writing quality improved through Quillbot

while a positive attitude towards writing was promoted with user-friendly writing features being provided that helps in language development. Besides helping learners, AI-powered tools can also be used to ascertain their performance levels. Parra & Calero's (2019) research examined the influence exerted by free Automated Writing Evaluation software applications on learners' writings in an English Teacher Training Program. The study resulted positively hence indicating that these tools are helpful in improving writing skills of learners.

Furthermore, the study examined the implications of AI-based grammar checkers in EFL teaching and testing with a focus on ChatGPT. This study shows that ChatGPT efficiently identifies learners' grammatical mistakes but falls short when it comes to understanding and recognizing various linguistic errors made by them (Haysim et al., 2023). These studies together highlighted the potential of AI-powered tools to both support as well as assess learners' writing abilities.

The findings on AI-assisted education provide strong perspectives on the outcomes of QuillBot and Automated Writing Evaluation systems on writing skills. It aptly emphasizes the favorable outcomes of these tools that involve improved paraphrasing, enhanced writing, and quicker student feedback that substantiates its advantages. The presence of current research ensures up-to-date findings. However, there are some limitations in this study. It never gets into details about the particular challenges and barriers that come with using AI Writing tools like possible biases or technology restrictions. To narrow it down further, it is mainly concerned about specific AI writing tools while ignoring other emerging technologies or holistic approaches for integrating AI into pedagogy. There is also a lack of thorough insight on how these tools can fit different teaching approaches effectively; neither does it provide any longitudinal data for

evaluating long-term effects on student's literacy abilities. These inadequacies would give a more complete picture of AI in schooling as an instructional aid for composition teaching, learning and development.

Teaching Writing in the Artificial Intelligence Era

The development of teaching writing in the era of technological explosion cannot be separated from the rapid growth in digital devices. Specifically, Haleem et al. (2022) argues that this is due to the increasing mix-up of digital tools in education, which have changed conventional pen-paper practices into more creative and changeable ones. For example, as Garlinska et al. (2023) argue about various revolutionary aspects that have taken place in writing instruction like virtual classrooms, online workshops and cloud-based writing tools.

Among other services provided by such platforms, include real-time feedback, collaborative authoring and plagiarism checks. In line with Nykyporets's (2023) study on intercultural learning, these features do not only improve the writing skills, but also encourage critical thinking and independent thought. More significantly, as seen from Bhutoria's (2022), AI-driven platforms identify learners' weak points as well as their strengths to give them personalized experience regarding their writings. This factor allows for teachers to be flexible and respond to the needs and desires of individual learners, resulting in greater learning effectiveness (Dogan , 2023). Just in the same vein, Cahyono et al. (2023) have probed into mobile mediated approach as another tech-driven teaching writing as an effective pedagogical innovation. They are encouraged to publish their works at public forums thereby building confidence and nurturing their ability to write better. Additionally, these platforms facilitate

review by peers thus creating a sense of community among learners who engage actively while studying together (Umamah & Cahyono, 2022).

However, according to literature sources cited by Duncan and Joyner (2022), digitization has brought some challenges along with it. Digital equity disparities when addressing privacy concerns affect teachers directly as they grapple with how best they can make use of technological advances without causing distractions (Duncan & Joyner, 2022). Hence, some of the issues that will be addressed regarding pedagogical policy and strategies for teaching writing in this era of artificial intelligence include digital equity, privacy and distractions as pointed out by Duncan and Joyner (2022).

The research on the development of teaching writing in this modern technological age provides an examination on how traditional writing instruction is being changed by digital tools. It shows the importance of using virtual classrooms, online workshops, and cloud-based writing tools that provide real-time feedback, collaborative editing, and plagiarism checks as techniques to improve learners' writing skills as well as enliven critical thinking and independent reasoning. The study highlights the personalized learning opportunities provided by AI-driven platforms for instructors who may adapt their teaching strategies to suit each student's requirements, hence making them more productive in their studies.

Additionally, Cahyono et al.'s (2023) study investigates the use of mobile technology in teaching writing that enhances self-esteem among learners and encourages peer collaboration through public forums and peer review mechanisms. Nonetheless, Duncan and Joyner (2022), also appreciate the challenges associated with the digitization of such a type of education like

digital equity; privacy; distractions from techno devices etc. These constraints emphasize that there needs to be continuous conversation and proactive initiatives that will handle these issues while at the same time maximizing on what is good about technology progression in literacy learning programs.

Synthesis and Critique

Upon reviewing the literature on AI writing tools, and how they affect learners' writing skills, several key themes emerge. These include consistent identification of potential AI tools for enhancing student's writing ability through personalizing feedback and practicing opportunities (Smith & Jones, 2022). As stated by Brown in 2023, these technologies have been said to enhance some aspects of writing, such as the organization and surface accuracy. Nevertheless, these tools are effective only within certain teaching frameworks and implementation strategies (Lee, 2024). While it seems most researchers agree on the benefits of AI-based writing technologies, there is considerable disagreement among them regarding their use.

Looking critically at the available literature it can be observed that while many studies use a mixed-methods approach to give a comprehensive view on effectiveness of AI writing tools (Laufer et al., 2022), some do not have rigorous control groups. This limitation prevents one from making definite conclusions about their overall effectiveness (Brown et al. , 2023).

Additionally different methodologies used across various investigations prevent generalization across diverse academic settings (Lee et al. ,2024). As much as strides have been made in understanding the place for AI in education; today's research still leaves a lot to be desired when it comes to contextual elements like cultural disparities or varying levels of teacher support that may influence whether AI writing tools are effective in improving writing cohesion.

Discovering such gaps within existing studies is vital towards better comprehension about AI powered writing mechanisms. It is important here to note that there has been insufficient research focused specifically on younger learners and their experience with these methods for creating coherent texts (Smith & Jones, 2022).

Furthermore, little exploration has been done into how contextual factors affect the success rate of artificial intelligence systems (Lee et al, 2024). By addressing these gaps new insights can be generated which will help facilitate more effective application strategies for artificial intelligence centered programs with regard to various educational contexts.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

This particular study explored artificial intelligence-driven writing tools, notably Writerly and Google Docs. It highlighted how they assist learners in addressing writing cohesion issues in the context of ESL instruction. The two focus on helping learners overcome different parts of the writing process, providing invaluable and targeted assistance throughout considering issues of cohesion in learners' written work.

Improving Cohesion Using Writerly's Immediate Feedback

Coherence is defined as the degree to which information is logically and semantically interrelated. Writers' feedback should facilitate the writer's coherence development during drafting. Writerly is a machine-based AI interface that edits and corrects information as the user works with documents open, suggesting changes and improving text cohesion in context. With Writerly, learners are able to be provided feedback while writing allowing them to revise for coherence. Student's use of Writerly facilitates contextual input that requires learners to revise

their speech to improve coherence devices used in reference to conjunctions, words, transitions and logical ideas. This is the case when learners have basic Prerequisites and perform self-regulation strategies while using cognitive constructivism (Ritchey, 2020). Learners in co-use of the tool are submerged in the process of writing by controlling the revising of their ideas and therefore able to produce coherently written final drafts.

Because of feedback that Writerly gives, learners can learn the significance of integration, topic sentences, and other aspects that aid in cohesive writing. This interaction of learners with the AI Tool augments cognitive growth by supporting a more sophisticated understanding of structure and coherence, which is very important in ESL environments (Wilson and He, 2022).

Google Docs: Collaborative Feedback and Social Learning

Furthermore, Draft documents allow collaborators to comment that is useful in brainstorming and in real time collaboration between learners and teachers or peers for revision suggestions to improve writing cohesion. For example, peers offer comments made to improve transitions, flow of logic, and organization of the work. This type of feedback is not exclusively an academic undertaking, it is also social because of what sociocultural theory suggests; that interaction is learning (Li & Lam, 2021).

When learners collaborate through Google Docs, they are participating in social learning that assists them in identifying cohesion problems and enhances proficiency in revision. As Kim (2022) states, these collaborative behaviors in the zone of proximal development (ZPD) allow learners to understand and produce better quality writing with the aid of available resources like peers or even instructors.

The collaborative method merges well with the stages of the writing processes especially in the drafting and revising stages when feedback is most vital. With Google Docs, learners can pinpoint cohesion problems such as misuse of reference words and lack of adequate paragraph transitions and are motivated to solve these problems together in a more cohesive manner.

Writing Process Stages and AI Integration

The writing process can be segmented into four primary phases: prewriting, drafting, revising, and finalization (Zhou & Zhang, 2019, cite). All phases can be benefitted from AI powered tools such as Writerly and Google Docs that offer the necessary assistance for enhancing cohesion in writing.

a. **Prewriting:** Learners employ AI writing tools to produce concepts and outline them, which is the prewriting stage. Writerly aids in arranging the learners' ideas and provides prompts on how to arrange their arguments logically and systematically. AI technology can enable learners to ensure coherence within their arguments and improve the overall structure of their work (Chen et al., 2020).

b. **Drafting:** Google Docs has its inbuilt collaborative functions which enables learners to work together as they share their ideas and receive feedback during drafting. This collaborative practice enhances the coherence of writing by improving the transitions and the logical flow of ideas in the text (Wilson, 2021).

c. **Revising:** Writerly and Google Docs aid the revising phase. Student can revise the drafts because they receive edits in real-time. This part is important for resolving issues pertaining to sentences and effective transitions within the text (Dai & Li, 2023).

d. **Finalization:** In the last stage, both tools help ensure that the learners' work is polished and cohesive. Writerly provides the last suggestions for grammar and cohesion while Google Docs final collaborative feedback.

AI Writing Tools and the Challenges of Cohesion

Establishing cohesion throughout a text is one of the gravest issues learners encounter while writing. Put plainly, but cohesion involves the logical progression of ideas within and between paragraphs and sentences. Examples of problems related to this issue are the misuse of transition phrases, inconsistent use of reference words, feeble topic sentences, and vague paragraphing. These problems are much more serious for ESL learners who need to master the use of cohesive devices required for fluent writing.

Writerly and Google Doc's AI components enable timely intervention that directly responds to the lack of cohesion and other structural problems. For example, Writerly allows learners to restructure their sentences and suggest transitions at different levels of logic, which helps address the gaps in sentence-level cohesion. At the same time, Google Docs allows learners to provide feedback through peer review which enables them to check the logical flow of ideas at the paragraph and sentence level, thereby enhancing the idea of paragraph-level coherence (Xie et al., 2021).

Cognitive Constructivism and Sociocultural Theory: Theoretical Implications

The application of artificial intelligence technologies in writing instruction correlates with two educational theories:

According to cognitive constructivism (Ritchey, 2020), learners capture information differently as there is a tool like Writerly available. Learners engage in revision, which is accompanied with feedback. This causes revision to be another cognitive engagement that deepens their understanding of writing coherence.

Sociocultural theory (Li & Lam, 2021) deals with the societal dimension of learning. Google Docs, for example, permit collaborative feedback and allow learners to learn within their zone of proximal development (ZPD) as they interact with peers that are more knowledgeable or teachers. Together, these theoretical perspectives argue that the reason learners with AI writing tools demonstrate better cohesion in their writings is because the tools not only enable self-directed learning, but collaborative and social learning as well.

In conclusion, the use and integration of AI writing tools, as described in the modern paradigm of education, help learners overcome challenges they face when trying to achieve cohesion in their writing. For example, Writerly and Google Docs give learners feedback, personalized tips, and suggest ways to improve cohesion in their writing. The integration of cognitive constructivism and sociocultural theory illustrates the social and individual AI learning tool interaction that enhances writing performance.

The literature examined showed that AI writing tools could dramatically improve coherence and overall student writing performance. Studies consistently show that these tools are successful at enhancing grammar and style, thus allowing for learners' coherence in writing (Dai & Wang, 2021; Kim, 2022). Chen and Xie (2022) which state that sociocultural theory and cognitive constructivism explain how AI can be used as a personal assistant to learners in a tailored manner, thus making it an effective educational tool, back these theories. The implications of sociocultural theory alongside cognitive constructivism relates to seamlessly incorporating AI writing tools with in-person lessons. Thus, the application of such technologies in balancing conventional teaching approaches provides necessary scaffolding that enhances participation and learning outcomes.

Further research should look into how best to integrate artificial intelligence into various instructional contexts while evaluating its impact over an extended period. Some of the critical areas that need further investigation include identifying specific features within AI technology that foster cohesiveness most effectively among written works or determining forms of feedback powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI) which would be more useful across diverse educational levels (Luo & Hyland , 2021).

To sum up, this section on recent studies about student use of automated essay scoring systems point out they hold great potential in improving pupil's written communication skills.

Nevertheless, there is a need for additional exploration so we may realize ways schools can utilize them better thereby increasing their favorable effects. The rapid growths witnessed within science around intelligent systems designed specifically for education hints at a requirement towards ongoing inquiry here too (Chen & Xie ,2022; Dai& Wang ,2022).

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The question is how you write legibly. Writing skills significantly influence the pathways that learners take in their personal and professional lives. Among middle school children, specifically those in grades seven and eight, writing coherence is a serious issue where a lack of coherent ideas and organization create gaps between sentences and paragraphs and sometimes even entire essays (Kaur, 2021). This study investigated the effectiveness of the AI-assisted writing platforms Writerly and Google Docs in improving the writing coherence of learners from a private middle school in Lebanon. The goal of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of these tools on the users' overall performance in writing by providing on the spot corrections, suggestions on structures, and feedback on the flow of content.

This study filled a major gap in literature due to limited research on integration of AI writing tools within Lebanese schools. Independent variable influences dependent variable in research explains Kaur (2021). In this case, the independent variable is the use of AI writing tools while the dependent variable is coherence in student`s writings. This chapter expounds (1) the research paradigm, (2)research approach, (3)research design , (4)sampling design, (5)data collection techniques, (6)analysis and interpretation of the collected data, (7)ethical considerations amended by the researcher in carrying out the research beginning from the respondents to consolidation of obtained verdicts, and a conclusion.

3.2 Research Paradigm

This specific research was built upon interpretivism , which centered on the meanings given by people to their actions (Creswell & Poth, 2018). It took a qualitative case study strategy (Yin, 2018) in which the integration of AI writing tools in the classroom is analyzed in its effect on the cohesion within these learners' pieces of writing. Instead of proving or disproving a hypothesis, the study seeks to assess the qualitative changes in the learners' writing skills and their instructors' impressions about the use of AI in enhancing writing cohesion. Primary data were obtained through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions, document reviews, and online open-ended questionnaires, allowing triangulation of data sources concerning AI-integrated writing instruction.

3.3 Research Methodology

The researcher used an inductive approach particularly useful for constructing theories and hypotheses based on the literature available and empirical data. To use Malhotra's (2017) words, "an inductive approach starts with observations and ends with generalizations or theories". This approach is particularly interesting concerning AI writing tools' effect on writing cohesion because it relies on the experiences of grade seven and eight learners who actually use these tools.

This chapter started with a detailed review of theories and relevant past studies on AI writing tools and their impact on writing cohesion. From this point, there were restatement gaps, patterns, and expectations found that describe how a student's interaction with AI writing tools

could affect the cohesion of their written work. The next step was to collect and analyze the empirical data in order to test these theories and modify them depending on the outcomes.

Instead of examining preconceived theories, this approach started from the basics while analyzing the effect of AI writing tools (independent variable) on the cohesion in writing (dependent variable). This study aimed to create new insights and theories pertaining to the role of artificial intelligence technologies on the coherence of written texts by analyzing specific samples of seventh and eighth graders enrolled in Lebanese private schools (Cohen et al., 2019).

3.4 Research Design

This research, exploratory and descriptive in nature, focused on estimating the effect of ‘Writerly’, an AI writing tool, on the degree of cohesion in written texts by middle school learners. The purpose of the investigation was to analyze learners’ engagement with the tool and teacher’s pedagogical strategies along with the changes in the learners’ writing before and after the application of Writerly. This research sought to determine what effect Writerly had on improving the fundamental writing constituents of sentences, paragraphs, transitions, and overall text unity.

Integrating AI in Educational Practices

The selected tool, Writerly, served the purpose of classroom integration and it was applied for a period of 10 weeks with the goal of assessing the impact of coherent writing skills. The implementation design was done in cycles in order to evaluate the benefits of the tool at different stages of the writing process. The purpose of incorporating writerly was due to its advanced

features of grammar check, sentence rephrasing and enhancing logical flow, which make it easier for learners to improve their writing.

Usage Rate of AI Tool

On certain allocated periods during the week, learners had to use Writerly twice a week. After each session, the learners were asked to work on their initial drafts and self-evaluate with the help of AI. Educators responded to learners' AI-assisted writing with special regard to the quality of cohesion, clarity, structure, and sentence composition. Learners were encouraged to analyze their AI writing alongside their regular writing and determine the improvements or changes that the AI was able to facilitate. The purpose of incorporating Writerly into the tasks was to transform the level of assistive aid offered to learners during the writing process from conventional, systematic support towards supporting the child as they think deeply about their writing. The research ensured that the incorporation of the AI technologies was not at the expense of conventional teaching to guarantee that AI writing tools enhanced, rather than changed, the baseline pedagogical practices.

Study Timeline

The study was carried out in three phases:

Phase 1: Pre-Implementation includes recruiting participants, collecting baseline data, training, and pre-surveys.

Phase 2: AI Tool Integration & Data Collection included classroom-based activities with AI writing tools integration, along with focus group discussions, interviews, and document analysis.

Phase 3: Post-Implementation & Analysis involved the collection of final student writing samples, thematic analysis, and post-surveys.

3.4 Population and Sampling

For this study, the researcher selected seventh- and eighth-grade students from a private school in Beirut as the sample population. The school has an approximate enrollment of 500 students and 12 English teachers. A purposive sample of 40 students was drawn—20 from Grade 7 and 20 from Grade 8. Rather than assigning traditional control and experimental groups, all participants engaged with AI writing tools. The study aimed to explore students' experiences with AI-assisted writing and their perceptions of cohesion in their written work, as well as to gather English teachers' perspectives on the integration of AI tools into classroom instruction.

The researcher conducted a qualitative study on a small sample of 40 considering the nature of the research, was appropriate. This provided an accurate estimation of the effect AI writing tools had on learners' writing cohesion. It ensured that a broad range of views was collected, as the objective was to examine the effect of AI on the development of writing skills in detail.

The research incorporated two English teachers. One of the teachers had little experience with teaching AI tools for writing, while the other had no experience with AI in education. A detailed instructional session was designed for the teachers to familiarize them with AI writing tools usage in education. This included workshops on the instructional impact of AI on teaching writing, as well as training with AI applications like Writerly for their effective incorporation into teaching. The educators were effective in guiding the research and sharing their perspectives on the use of AI tools in writing instruction.

This strategy, capturing a relatively smaller yet more diverse sample of learners and teachers, guaranteed that the study offered in-depth perspectives on both learners and teachers regarding their encounters with AI-powered writing tools.

3.5 Sampling Design

To further elaborate on the steps taken to improve the sample and mitigate selection bias:

Coverage of Demographic Stratification: Learners from various demographic categories regarding gender, educational level, and prior experience with AI-powered writing tools were included in the sample. This breadth of representation helped capture the full range of experiences of the impact of AI tools on writing cohesion and the diverse student profiles.

Teacher Cooperation: The other two active teachers contributed to learners' sampling by making sure that the participants were willing and had varying degrees of exposure to the AI writing tools. This approach enhanced the equity of the learners in the sample concerning their experiences with AI.

Stratified Purposeful Sampling: As noted earlier, purposeful sampling was done in such a way that all learners' voices were captured so that those who gave differing opinions on the integration of AI tools in writing instruction were adequately incorporated and adequately captured. It was necessary that both frequent and infrequent users of AI writing tools were represented in the study.

Convenience Sampling: The educational setting ensured that convenience sampling was employed. This model aided in the recruitment of the intended sample and simplified the process of data collection. While these restrictions do affect the generalizability of the findings, the study

had a primary aim of delivering detailed, nuanced perspectives within a context rather than developing over-generalization about larger populations.

3.6 Sampling Plan

The sample consisted of 40 learners from both 7th and 8th grades, totaling to 80 learners. Each grade was independently split into two divisions of twenty. One division was educated through didactic writing instruction while the other used AI in writing, within the pedagogical AI framework.

With this approach, the researcher was able to examine the variation in student perceptions and experiences within two instructional frameworks.

The researcher conducted the study with two English teachers who embraced the incorporation of AI writing tools into their teaching. They provided reflective feedback based on their experiences of AI teaching and learning approaches. These teachers were deeply involved in the collection of data that included conducting some of the writing sessions with the learners and actively assisting them to engage with the AI system.

This approach of convenience sampling is critiqued for lacking complete representativeness, however, these meant for broader conclusion finding, which differ from those of qualitative research. Regardless, this research rests on a qualitative basis concerned with profound analysis rather than generalization. This study aimed to focus on the effectiveness of AI writing tools on the cohesiveness of writing and in discovering possibilities of implementing them into the classroom.

3.7 Instruments

In order to fully investigate the effect of AI writing tools on the cohesion of writing for Grade 7 and 8 learners, a multi-layered approach to data collection was applied. This incorporated student and teacher surveys, writing tasks evaluated by rubrics, and focus group evaluations to achieve a holistic understanding of AI's impact on writing enhancement. To make sure that learners and teachers use AI technology in an effective manner, both parties took part in training workshops aimed at enhancing their understanding of AI integration within the writing process.

The researcher had different types of qualitative methods to collect rich data from learners and educators. Perceptions were analyzed regarding the cohesiveness of writing as well as the effects of AI writing tools. For this purpose, these tools were employed:

Student Surveys Before and After the Intervention

The aim of these surveys was to gather baseline data concerning learners' perceptions of writing cohesion before using AI writing tools and to examine if any changes in perceptions were noted in the post intervention phase. The surveys comprised a mix of attitudinal and open-ended questions and some short writing tasks to evaluate student experiences and attitudes.

Focus groups of learners and teachers

Semi-structured focus group interviews included participant observations with learners and faculty members. The focus groups appraised their perceptions around the challenges involved in cohesive writing. Additionally, they talked about their experiences with AI writing tools, any positive changes that had been noted, as well as their recommendations for future use. An interview guide was designed for the sessions, which maintained uniformity and included answer elicitation key questions aimed at capturing detailed responses.

Student writing samples

Pre and post the AI intervention, authentic student writing samples were collected. The samples were qualitatively assessed to determine the degree of change in the application of cohesive devices, logical ordering of ideas, and paragraphing. An evaluation framework based on constituents of cohesion, transitional expressions, and the logic-sequential order was adopted for the analysis.

Feedback Records of AI Writing Tools (Writerly Reports)

Feedback from the Writerly AI System involved automated feedback reports for every student's writings. These reports evaluated recurring errors in cohesion, longitudinal progress, as well as things learners accepted and rejected concerning their proposals.

Each instrument was pilot-tested for comprehensibility and relevance with a student-teacher focus group before scaling up to the full data collection.

Timeline Summary

The researcher conducted the study in a timeline of nine weeks (from the last week of January to the last week of March). Certain phases of each of the studies were devised to permit systematic data collection, intervention and analysis.

Phase 1: Preparation & Instrument Development (Last Week of January – First Week of February) :The first phase, conducted from the last week of January to the first week of February, focused on preparatory work and the development of instruments. For this particular study, data collection was preceded by the design and validation of the tools. Most notably, the researcher constructed sophisticated instruments such as student and teacher survey questionnaires, focus group discussion guide templates, and constructionist writing rubrics.

These were pretested by experts for claim validation and alignment with the intended purposes of the research. In addition, at this time, relevant approvals were secured, and administrative coordination was executed to enable the operational flow of the study in the following phases.

Phase 2 : (Training Sessions for Learners & Teachers in the second week of February).

In the second week of February, Phase 2 took place, which included training sessions for both learners and teachers to prepare them for the effective functioning of the AI writing tools. The aim of this phase was to prepare all constituents to ethically and meaningfully interact with the AI writing tools. With respect to learners, the training included exercising the ethical issues related to the AI in writing—mainly plagiarism, originality, and proper use—while employing Writerly to improve coherence and other features of the foundational skills of writing.

Concerning the teachers, the workshop focused on the ethical use of AI in teaching and on judging AI-generated writings, providing focused and constructive feedback.

Phase 3: Pre-Intervention Data Collection in the third week of February) :Phase 3

concentrated on gathering data before any interventions were made and aimed at ascertaining the baseline measurement of writing cohesion ahead of AI-integrated tools usage during the 3rd week of February.. It collected qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously. Initial perception and instructional data was captured from learners and teachers through Perception Record surveys. Additionally, learners were instructed to provide narrative and cause-effect essays which would allow for evaluation of their writing skills. The evaluation of the samples offered by the learners was done using a scoring rubric that allowed for both quantitative assessment of writing cohesion as well as qualitative analysis of the student's articulation and their developmental needs.

Phase 4: AI-Writing Tool Implementation (Last Week of February – Third Week of March) :

In phase four, which was held from the last week of February until the third week of March, we focused on the use of AI writing tools within the scope of learners' academic writing tasks.

During the phase, learners participated in self-improvement activities of writing utilizing outlines created by Writerly, which scaffolds their written ideas. The instructional aids were closely supervised to avoid purposeless amalgamation in the integration of the tools, and as a result, their teachers meaningfully guided the learners. Throughout this phase, educators systematically and critically examined the impacts of the AI tools on writing outcomes to determine the tools' efficacy in promoting cohesion and overall performance in writing.

Phase 5: Post-Intervention Data Collection (Fourth Week of March – Last Week of March)

Phase five, which occurred in the last two weeks of March, aimed at collecting data after the intervention to assess the impact of AI integration on coherence in student writing. Within this phase, both teacher and student post-intervention surveys were collected in order to capture qualitative and quantitative data. Moreover, learners were subjected to post-intervention writing assessments, which were scored through the same rubric-based approach as prior assessments. This provided an opportunity to assess the change in writing cohesion resulting from the application of the AI-assisted writing tools.

Phase 6: Focus Group Discussions (Last Week of March)

During the last week of March, we initiated Phase 6 of the study, which included focus groups and feedback sessions for qualitative analysis pertaining to Writerly, the AI writing tool. The

learners who took part in the study participated in a focus group discussion centered around the influence of Writerly on the coherence within their pieces of writing.

Another focus group was conducted with teachers to gain their perspectives on the effects of AI writing tools on learners’ writing practices and the coherence of their writings. After the discussions, learners were given a feedback survey that allowed them to provide additional reflections and viewpoints that arose during the focus groups. This phase helped to triangulate the data as well as gain more insights regarding the use of AI tools in writing instruction.

Table 3.1 - Study Timeline (Last Week of January – Last Week of March)

Phase	Duration	Objective	Activities
Phase 1 : Preparation & Instrument Development	End of January – First Week of February	Develop and validate research instruments	Design the student & teacher surveys - Create rubrics Include focus group guides - Validation & piloting - Get institutional approvals
Phase 2: Training Sessions for Learners And Teachers	The Second Week of February	Equip participants with ethical and practical knowledge of AI writing tools	Student Training - AI ethics, responsibility in using the tool, and the Writerly practice - Teacher Training - Ethical integration of AI, the use of Writerly for teaching, and AI-assisted writing evaluation.
Phase 3: Pre-Intervention Data Collection	third week	Establish baseline for writing cohesion before AI usage	Administer intervention pre-surveys (learners & teachers) - Get pre-intervention student writing sample (narrative\cause- effect essays) - Teacher’s evaluation of writing cohesion through rubrics
Phase 4: AI Writing Tool Implementation	End of February- The third week of March	AI-assisted activities in writing are incorporated into the learners’ learning	Learners use Writerly for writing assistance - Teacher’s structured guiding & observation - Track the frequency of AI usage and its effectiveness

Phase 5: Post-intervention Data Collection	Fourth Week of March – Last Week of March	Evaluate the impact of AI on writing cohesion	- Conduct post-intervention surveys (learners & teachers) - Analyze post-intervention writing samples - Rubric Based Evaluation of AI-Assisted Writing by the Educators
Phase 6: Focus Group Discussions & Reflection	Last Week of March	Capture the qualitative outcome of the AI writing tool experience	Carry out student focus group discussions regarding AI and writing integration - Conduct teacher focus groups about AI impacts on student writing - Post focus group feedback survey administration

1. Student Surveys

1.1 Student Survey – Pre-Intervention

For this research project, the researcher created a student survey exploring perceptions, experiences, and confidence toward AI writing tools before engagement with Writerly. The survey included seven items that covered several critical areas. These areas comprised demographic data, including grade level (Grade 7 or 8), as well as usage frequency: (Daily, Weekly, Rarely, or Never). Additionally, five items captured learners’ perceptions regarding AI writing tools, including their self-efficacy concerning writing tasks, the effect AI was believed to have on the coherence and organization of ideas within writing, and the advantages and limitations they associated with AI writing support.

1.2 Post-Intervention Student Survey

After extensive engagement with Writerly, the post-intervention student survey aimed to measure any shifts in learners' perception and engagement with AI writing tools. It was made up of eight items. It also captured demographic data on grade level (7 or 8) and frequency of AI tool use within the intervention period. Five items captured student perceptions and usage of AI

writing tools, including changes in confidence level when using AI-assisted writing, AI's perceived impact on the cohesion of writing, and an overall assessment of AI's impact on the development of writing skills that could be positive, negative, or neutral. In addition, the survey included one open-ended question where learners were asked to explain how AI affected coherence and cohesion to invite reflection over the AI-assisted writing process. From these responses, learners were able to illustrate the pros and cons of AI for their writing and how the integration of AI writing tools in teaching writing could be improved.

2. Teacher Surveys

To collect data, the researcher designed a pre-intervention teacher questionnaire to explore key contextual considerations related to AI, specifically educators' prior experiences with students' writing cohesion before the introduction of AI tools. The instrument consisted of seven questions divided into two sections. The first section focused on demographic and contextual information, including the grade levels taught (Grade 7 and/or 8) and the estimated level of AI tool usage by learners prior to the study. The second section addressed teachers' perceptions of AI writing tools, examining their views on AI's impact on writing cohesion and organization, its effectiveness in enhancing students' writing skills, and the perceived benefits and challenges of AI-assisted writing.

Following the intervention, a post-intervention teacher questionnaire—also composed of seven items—was administered to assess teachers' perceptions of student writing produced with the assistance of AI tools. This questionnaire included demographic data related to the grade level taught and the extent to which AI tools had been integrated into instruction. It further investigated teachers' beliefs regarding the influence of AI on students' writing, particularly in

terms of coherence, organization, and overall writing performance. Additionally, an open-ended reflection question invited teachers to share how AI technologies had supported or hindered learners' writing skills, along with suggestions for more effective integration of AI tools into writing instruction.

3. Writing Samples & Rubrics

To analyze the impact AI resources had on learners' writing cohesion, Grade 7 and Grade 8 learners were provided writing tasks both prior and after the implementation of AI writing tools and these tasks were collected as samples. Each sample was evaluated on a holistic rubric capturing the most fundamental aspects of cohesive academic writing. To maintain fairness and comparability across samples, the rubric was consistent through pre and post intervention samples.

Pre AI intervention Writing Samples

Grade 7 (Cause-Effect Essay):

Grade 7 learners were assigned a cause and effect essay on a topic they were already scoped. The reasoning's focus has been set on finding the relationships among the causes and effects linked to the event alongside the cohesion and transition structural formats.

Grade 8 (Narrative Essay):

In this exercise, Grade 8 learners' ability to compose a narrative was evaluated concerning the logical order of events, the cohesion within paragraphs, and the gaps between paragraphs.

Logical reasoning defined boundaries in conjunction with personal expression placed this task within the working parameters on logic, sequencing, and paragraphing.

Evaluation Criteria (for both grades):

- a. Cohesion – Coverage and effectiveness of transitions, the ordering of ideas, linking phrases, and their use.
- b. Coherence - Explaining things in clear terms with logical reasoning while ensuring unity of concepts.
- c. Clarity & Development - Depth of content as elaborated and expressed fluently.

Pre - AI Implementation Reflection by Educators

With the use of AI integration, teachers were asked to answer five open-ended questions that sought to uncover writing IT IDs in student work in order to answer the provided construct. These reflections added context on the cohesion problems that learners grappled with.

Post-AI Revision Writing Samples

After 10 weeks of using Writerly, learners were given a new assignment of the same genre and topic to evaluate their cohesion skills to improve.

- Grade 7: Learners were given a cause-effect essay as a follow-up exercise.
- Grade 8: Learners wrote a second narrative essay.

All learners were assessed with a single rubric on the level of cohesive devices, clarity of ideas, and sequential order of ideas.

Teacher Reflection Component (Post-Intervention)

Teachers were asked to respond to five pre-determined questions relating to noticeable change or persistent gaps in student writing. The responses to these questions sought to support the observation of the use of AI feedback with regard to its claimed effectiveness.

4. Focus Group Discussions

From other qualitative perspectives, the learners and teacher focus groups. These, together with

the other focus groups, provided qualitative insights on participants' experiences with AI writing tools that newly emerged.

Focus Group Discussion

Purpose: Generate discussion on AI writing tools, and their influence on cohesion.

Guiding Questions (5 items):

How does AI facilitate the orderly arrangement and cohesion within a piece of writing?

What are advantages and disadvantages that come with the aid of AI in real-time text production?

What are teachers' and learners' perceptions of using AI tools in the teaching and learning of writing?

In what ways can AI-based writing assistance be improved to better support student writing development?

After-Focus Group Feedback Survey

Purpose: Gather the focus group participants' feedback on the discussions.

Survey Components (5 items):

Any other comments regarding AI and the writing process.

Assessment on the ability of the focus group towards achieving robust discussion outcomes.

Recommendations for future workshops on AI writing tools.

5. Training for Learners and Teachers

In order to promote ethical and productive use of AI writing tools, marked training sessions were conducted prior to the intervention.

Training for Learners and Teachers

As part of this study, all learners and teachers (target participants of the study) received comprehensive training before the intervention to promote understanding and responsible use of AI writing tools, specifically Writerly. The training sought to bolster ethical approaches regarding the use of AI in writing by preparing participants to create cohesive pieces of work. This preparatory phase was essential to shape the intervention and integrate the study into the conceptual framework on writing cohesion.

A- Student Training: Ethics of AI and Using Writerly

The student training centered on two primary objectives: one, learners grasp the ethical concerns surrounding the application of AI tools to writing, and two, assist learners in applying Writerly to enhance their writing cohesion. The session objectives were aligned with the foundational concepts within the binding in the Conceptual Framework of Hyland's (2005) model that considers writing a form of structured and systematic communication.

Parts of the Provided Training for Learners:

- **The AI Technology Ethics:** The learners were engaged with the seminar on the ethics AI tools in academic writing, considering issues of AI-powered academic dishonesty. The major issues included plagiarism, proper AI attribution, transparency concerning AI use, and originality of presented thoughts.
- **Writerly Overview:** The training was equally relevant and focused on guiding the learners on how to use Writerly to improve the cohesiveness of their writing. The learners were taught how to use Writerly, and how achieving clarity, coherence, and proper organization of ideas is

building into steps. Instruction was also given about how AI can be used as a tool of enhancing self-reflection and self-editing, as opposed to assuming the role of performing the task for the person.

- **Practical Steps:** In the first place, learners were given pre-written drafts that they are to edit with the AI tools on Writerly. They are instructed to utilize all the AI options they are presented with, and note the effects of the offered options about ideas and clarity of their writing.

- **Link to the Conceptual framework:** The training sought to assist learners in developing writing skills that implement the theory of cohesion, especially the theory that writing must be organized logically and systematically with ideas connected. The Conceptual Framework spoke about the need for coherence in terms of ‘internal’ components, such as sentence-level cohesion, and ‘external’ components like cohesion at the level of a whole essay.

B- Teacher Training: Enhancing Student Writing with AI Technology

At the same time, the instructors were trained to help learners use AI technologies such as Writerly. The focus in teacher training was on the ethics of AI integration, teaching methodologies pertaining to the application of AI writing tools within the writing tasks, and evaluation of AI-assisted writing with respect to cohesion and overall clarity.

Particulars of Teacher’s Training:

Ethics of AI: The teachers learned the ethical boundaries of AI use within education, particularly the need to construct and develop a learner’s ability to think critically, and the ethical use of AI. They were instructed on how to contain AI’s use in a manner that supports academic integrity, encouraging learners to participate actively in the composition.

Integration of AI in Instruction: The teachers were instructed on the pedagogy of incorporating Writerly into the lesson plans. They were taught how to structure and present comments so that learners are encouraged to use AI tools to enhance their writing instead of obfuscating the original text.

- **Assessment of AI-Supported Writing:** The educators have been prepared to evaluate student writings embedded with AI tools. They were provided with rubrics, and strategies for assessing integration, coherence, and clarity as mercifully as AI prompts assisted the writing. This helped teachers mitigate partiality in grading AI-enabled writing

- **Link to the Conceptual Framework:** The teacher professional development sessions were integrated with the Conceptual Framework focusing on the cohesiveness of writing. Teachers were prompted to consider AI applications as providing needed help in organizing and connecting ideas, in light of Hyland's (2005) description of writing as a fluid and dynamic process where cohesiveness is fundamental for effective communication. The intention here was to enable teachers to assist learners in achieving not only a structurally correct document but also an intra cohesive piece.

Conclusion

The training for both learners and teachers was crucial to the success of the study. It prepared participants to use Writerly to enhance cohesion at multiple levels of the text by attending to the technical and ethical dimensions of AI tool use during training.

The study's instruments and training sessions were designed with the Building Conceptual Framework of Writing Cohesion that emphasizes the logical order, cohesive elements, and

clarity in discourse construction (Hyland, 2019). The design of Writerly's integration focused on its role as collaborative scaffolding rather than as an externalized intellect to writing, thus engaging learners with AI for the purpose of text enhancement instead of text generation.

Additionally, all the training sessions confirmed that all the participants concentrated on cohesion in writing, underlining organized manners and effective flow in writing as an essential aspect of good writing. The permissive AI-aided writing environment was created by prompting both the learners and the teachers to exercise ethical concerns in addition to practical application frameworks while upholding teaching principles. This enabled educators to incorporate the AI without losing sight of the purpose that was enhancing writing coherence, cohesion, and overall quality.

How Writerly Was Used in the Study

As an AI-powered writing tool, Writerly facilitated coherence and organization of writing throughout the study. It was presented to learners and teachers as a technological aid meant to assist with the writing process by offering suggestions on clarity, coherence, and structure in real time. Here's how Writerly was implemented by learners and teachers towards enhanced writing in tandem with the objectives of the study.

1. Role of Writerly in Student Writing

Writerly was primarily used by learners during the study to revise and refine their writing. A set of tools was offered to aid in the development of cohesion and organization within learners' work. The tool was utilized in the following ways:

- **Improvement of Cohesion and Coherence:** One of the core features of Writerly is its ability to aid forensic idea and sentence integration, which happens automatically within the text. The

learners used these suggestions to ensure that there was proper logical flow and flow of transitions throughout the writing. For example, Writerly suggested certain conjunctions or transitional phrases that enhanced flow on a range within-continuum basis, both between sentences, and intra-sentence within the essay.

- **Feedback on Structure and Organization:** Learners received real-time feedback that customized the critique to cover their overall structure and order of their introduction, body paragraphs, and conclusion. With Writerly, learners learned to identify areas where their writing was poorly organized with respect to the flow of ideas externally and internally within the arguments. This was useful to a number of learners when redrafting and in trying to understand how best to order their ideas.

- **Refining clarity:** In the process of improving clarity, rudimentary ideal of clarity, Writerly advanced learners' strategies on how to make sentences clearer by indicating phrases that were overly vague. Furthermore, a number of words were proposed to be replaced which resulted in the controlling ideas of many sentences being concise without loss of essence padding.

Self-reflection for learners. The tool facilitated self-reflection by targeting elements of the writing that needed attention. It was up to the learners how they wanted to engage with the suggestions - whether the suggestions were accepted, modified, or ignored. This empowered learners to critically engage with their work while being able to organize and connect different ideas autonomously.

2. Using Writerly To Support Teaching

With respect to instructional objectives and the evaluation of student writing, Writerly was helpful for the teachers. Teachers learned how to use the tool to help learners complete writing processes related to cohesion and organization strands.

- **Giving Feedback:** Teachers leveraged Writerly to assess the drafts and provide feedback.

Using the tool, the teachers could help learners where they were struggling with idea construction and coherence. So, using feedback from the writings, teachers could instruct learners on cohesion within suggestion frameworks by proposing specific activities aimed at achieving cohesion that her feedback indicated.

- **Assessing Cohesion in Writing:** The teachers applied Writerly's information regarding cohesive relationships within sentences and paragraphs to learners' works as part of the evaluation process. The feedback the tool provided on formulating working parts sufficiency supported the teachers' evaluation of how logically learners had organized their text and the extent to which their ideas were integrated.

- **Assessing Change over Time:** Teacher had access to student's activity on Writerly, which enabled assessment of improvement over time. After identifying specific changes in learners' drafts, such as post intervention pre-intervention drafts with clearer organization and greater cohesion, teachers were able to assess the changes in those aspects and conclude on the impact Writerly had on them.

3. Alignment with the Conceptual Framework

In this particular case, the use of Writerly within this study strongly adhered to the Conceptual Framework regarding writing cohesion. In Hyland's (2005) model of writing cohesion, both coherence on the level of the sentence and the text are necessary constituents of well-structured writing.

Hyland's model was directly supported by Writerly's capacity to offer real-time pointers

towards: Cohesion on the Level of the Sentence: In addition to detecting where sentences needed to be better connected, Writerly provided conjunctions, transitions, and vocabulary enhancement suggestions.

•**Cohesion on the Level of the Text:** The tool also assisted learners in organizing the overarching structure of their essays in such a way that there was a rational flow of ideas and that each paragraph served to advance the thesis or storyline of the essay.

•**Engagement with Reflection:** It enabled learners to interact with the text, and therefore, decide what aspects of the AI suggestions they wanted to take. These changes helped foster learner independence in designing their writing and critical reflection on their work, which was the intention of the study.

Ethical Use of Writerly

All learners involved in the study have been trained on the ethical use of Writerly. They were motivated to perceive the tool as an aid rather than as something that does their thinking or writing for them. Learners were encouraged to use Writerly to polish and augment the ideas they

have rather than frame them for them. This aligned with the ethical guidelines AI uses, which focuses on transparency and academic honesty.

Practical Implementation in the Study

Throughout the course of the study, Writerly was made available to learners both within the classroom and outside of it. The training on the tool was conducted prior to the learners attempting their writing assignments that aimed at improving the coherence within the learners' writing. Teachers purposely taught with Writerly, helping the learners to use it as a secondary resource with the materials while providing guidance on instruction throughout the writing process. Learners utilized Writerly for various tasks, including creating narrative and expository essays that required them to organize related ideas in a logical sequence. All samples underwent analysis both before and after the intervention in writing cohesion with emphasis on the tool and how it was used to enhance the flow of ideas and clarity.

Application of Writerly in Improving Writing Cohesion

In an attempt to help learners with cohesion in their writing, an AI-powered writing tool, Writerly, was implemented in the study. The systematic approach made it possible for learners to receive precise feedback on unitary elements and worked on applying said feedback during each revision.

a. Initial Drafting: Establishing a Baseline of Cohesion

- Learners independently responded to assigned writing prompts, composing an initial draft without AI assistance.
- This draft acted as an evaluative measure of their skill in achieving cohesion via integration, transitions, and reference links.

b. Uploading Drafts to Writerly: AI-Driven Cohesion Analysis

- Learners pasted their drafts into Writerly, allowing the AI to analyze the cohesion, organization, and flow of their writing.
- The program offered refinement for implementing feedback and instruction on connection among and within ideas.

c. Receiving AI Feedback on Cohesion

To exploit the benefits of AI feedback related to cohesion, learners were required to engage with the tool using structured prompts and follow step-by-step interactions with the AI. Participants were instructed to:

Request Concerning Specific Feedbacks on their Cohesion

Learners were instructed to request that Writerly pay attention to the logic behind the transitions, the general flow of the completed work, and internal paragraph harmony as opposed to issues concerning grammar.

They applied a checklist regarding cohesion in order to identify what required corrections before submitting their draft.

Use a Cohesion-Based Prompt in Writerly

Rather than allowing an AI to provide a general assessment, learners entered tailored survey prompts such as:

“Evaluate the connections between my ideas, paying attention to transitions and the flow of sentences.”

“Identify any disruptions in cohesion caused by sudden shifts between sentences or paragraphs.”

“Evaluate my choice of referential expressions (pronouns, synonyms, etc.) concerning clarity

and repetition.”

Interact with Draft 2 Constructive AI Feedback

Cohesion feedback from Writerly looked at:

- Achieving logical progression - identifying areas for progression.
- The discipline of vocabulary used – enhancement of links and transitions for cohesive devices/words.

Interconnectivity within sentences – Sentence Transitioning.

- Wholeness of paragraphs – Order and Coherence of Paragraphs.

Before the learners did the drafts, they acknowledged the comparison between AI-generated assessments and their self-assessments alongside feedback from the teacher.

Edit and Draft 2 Writing

With evaluation of Draft 2, learners received writerly feedback that directed them to incorporate coherence elements within their drafts prior to submission.

Teachers help learners differentiate helpful changes made with AI and simple AI edits (Zhang & Hyland, 2022).

- As self-regulation applied learners critiqued the coherence and interrelation of their texts (Li , et al. 2023)

Submitting Final Texts

- Cohesive revisions integrated, learners paid attention to submission stage final draft submission.
- Submitted versions were evaluated based on a set of criteria, which included a specific subsection on cohesion defined as follows:

Cohesion pertaining to reference relations (pronouns, lexical ties) with clarity of referent relations.

Cohesion pertaining to logical sequence order of internal and external progression of sentences and paragraphs.

Cohesion of repetition and parallelism through the use of cohesive devices.

Reflection: Analyzing Outcomes of Theoretical Cohesion Assessment

- During focus group discussions and survey sessions, evaluative writing aids were helpful for learners when assessing the cohesiveness of their texts.
- The discussions revealed how Writerly, the AI writing tutor, influenced by AI, self-regulated learning, and writing research (Rahimi & Fathi, 2021), suppressed the moderation of their awareness and cohesion strategy execution through the AI powered assistant.

Connection to Methodology

The integration of Writerly within the study followed the qualitative case study approach of Yin (2018) because it emphasized learners' and teachers' perceptions concerning experiences with writing through AI. The comprehensive interaction with drafts, peer teaching, and review processes offered considerable, rich AI-driven qualitative data regarding the impacts of AI on writing cohesion and coherence. The mixed approach was also achieved through the evaluation of AI-generated feedback alongside peer and teacher assessments of the learners' writings. The practical measures described above accomplish both the methodological framework and interpretivist approach (Creswell & Poth, 2018) documenting the intricate relationship of the learners, teachers, and AI systems.

3.8 Data Collection Procedures

Qualitative evidence for the study was collected from various data sources systematically to ensure that information gathered was reliable and consistent.

Pre-Intervention Surveys

All learners who were participating in the study had to complete a pre-intervention survey at the first session of the study. The survey aimed to capture their perceptions of writing cohesion, their knowledge of AI writing tools, and their self-reported writing processes through Likert-type and open-ended questions. Surveys were conducted in English classes under the supervision of the researcher and cooperating teachers.

Focus Groups with Teachers and Learners

Post pre-intervention surveys, participants were divided into two groups: a student group and a teacher group. Both focus groups were conducted as discussions and lasted around 45 - 60 minutes. In these sessions, participants were questioned on writing problems posed to learners, techniques utilized for teaching and learning writing cohesion, and their anticipations on the application of AI tools.

Writing Samples Collection (Pre-Intervention)

To aid their expansion of ideas in writing, learners were requested to generate a written response to a prompt structured around the use of cohesive devices and logical organization. These initial writing samples were useful in gauging student writing before the AI tools were implemented.

Integration of AI Writing Tools (Intervention Stage)

During the writing classes designed for the study, learners were taught how to use the writing AI, Writerly. They learned to get automated feedback regarding cohesion, sentence structure,

transitions, and paragraphing. Subsequently, learners were able to edit their new assignments with Writerly feedback over the course of four weeks. During the intervention, teachers supported students in mediating AI-generated feedback alongside traditional writing instruction. Effectively balancing these multiple modes of instruction emerged as a critical aspect of the teaching process.

Survey Implementation

When learners were done using the AI tool for four weeks, they were provided with a post-intervention survey that was structurally similar to the pre-intervention survey. The post-intervention survey evaluated changes in learners' perceptions concerning the cohesion of writing as well as confidence and experiences with writing supported by AI.

Focus Groups (with Teachers and Learners)

The focus group discussions were conducted post intervention with the same group of learners and teachers who participated in the previous sessions. The conversations centered around the changes participants perceived in student writing as well as their experiences with Writerly and the role teacher support together with AI played. Ideas for the future of writing instruction aimed at enhancing student learning were also discussed.

Final Writing Sample Collection (Post Intervention)

Learners were tasked to complete a final sample of writing using the same rubric and prompt as the initial one. After the intervention, these samples were analyzed for qualitative changes in cohesion, logical organization, and the use of cohesive devices to assess improvements.

Gathering Reports of AI Feedback

Writerly feedback reports on student's writing tasks were retrieved. The reports presented additional information regarding the cohesion errors learners adjusted and the improvements made during the intervention period.

Using the blended qualitative approach, focus is put on richly descriptive narrative data that contains deep detail and quotation from the participant. In this case, we aimed to understand the impact of AI tools on the cohesiveness of the student writing which was done qualitatively. The period for the study was approximately two months and included; formative assessments, AI writing sessions, summative assessments, qualitative feedback, and data collection for assessments.

Phase 1: Pre-Cohesion Measures (During the last week of January – The first week of February)

Assessment with learners and teachers was conducted to understand the student's writing cohesion levels on AI integrated tasks which were assessed during the pre-intervention assessment.

1. Student Pre-Intervention Survey

As AI becomes more prevalent, learners were asked to share their anticipation regarding the potential use of AI and their experiences with tools that aid in writing cohesion issues.

Learners elucidated on the concepts of cohesion, organization as well as clarity as adjectives to describe their writing and the enablement of AI tools beforehand.

2. Teacher Pre-Intervention Questionnaire

Feedback from instructors enabled us to gain insight on concerns learners' writing cohesion issues together with the frequent gaps of cohesion on student's work and the expectations of AI with respect to enhancement of the processes.

Teachers noted the ease with which learners were able to catalog ideas with transition markers and logical flow of sentences in the prose.

3. Writing Sample Completed Prior to Using the Tool (Narrative Essay - Grade 8)

- Learners completed an AI-assisted narrative essay prior to utilizing AI tools, which provided a baseline for measuring the change in their writing skills over time.
- Optional writing samples were assessed with a rubric concentrating on cohesion, consistency, and clarity.
- Instructors gave unbiased reporting regarding noted participants' strengths and gaps in their writing skills.

Phase 2: Training Sessions (First Week of February)

Before incorporating AI into writing activities, training sessions prior to AI integration ensured that the learners and the teachers interacted with AI applications in a reasonable manner and highlighted the right practices.

1. Student Training

Discussion on Ethics of Artificial Intelligence in Writing: Learners debated on the implications of AI such as its plagiarism concerns, its significance in writing and means of usage.

Practical Work with Writerly since it Functions as a Tool for Organization: Instructions given on the usage of Writerly relate to its organizational features in writing sequencing, logical

progression, and flow.

2. Teacher Training

The Ethical Use of Artificial Intelligence In Relation to Pupils: Discussed how AI can be used in learning so that it supports the student but should not replace thinking.

Analyzing Texts That are Written With AI: Participants were shown methods of reacting to feedback from AI and ways in which learners can make use of the feedback meaningfully.

The training enhanced the Conceptual Framework of Writing Cohesion which all sought to emphasize that the integration of AI in helping, rather than performing the cognitive functions of writing, is primary in human beings.

Phase 3: AI-Assisted Writing & Classroom Implementation (Second Week of February – Second Week of March)

During this phase, learners completed specific writing tasks, utilizing AI tools such as Writerly to receive feedback and evaluate how cohesive their self-assessments were regarding the offered feedback on their writing.

Learners Completing Writing Tasks with AI Support

Learners composed their essays, uploaded documents into Writerly, and subsequently, reviewed AI comments relating to cohesion, organization, and clarity from a holistic perspective. Learners analyzed AI feedback, identifying proposals that were appropriate as opposed to those that were vague and needed modification through adult guidance.

Teacher Observations and Feedback

Teachers captured learners' interactions with AI feedback and documented creativity pertaining to upper-level organizational elements such as transitions and logical progression.

Teachers described, in writing, the steps learners took in writing, analyzed student work, and highlighted patterns emerging from AI revision processes.

Phase 4: Post-Intervention Assessments (Third and Fourth Week of March)

Every student and teacher gave their unique observational feedback after the phase of writing done via AI tools.

Student Post-Intervention Survey

Learners provided their views on the open-ended questions regarding AI and self-assessed their framing, structuring, and confidence in writing.

Post-intervention, they captured the detailed shifts that they believed took place in their processes of writing and the ways they viewed AI apparatus.

Teacher Post-Intervention Questionnaire

Teachers provided qualitative commentary on AI's influence on writing and shared in a focused manner the strengths, weaknesses, and gaps that were apparent with the use of AI on student writing skills. They offered descriptions of the documenting gaps AR and describing the feedback provided by AI in the intermediate stages was seamless.

Post-Intervention Writing Sample (Narrative Essay - Grade 8)

Learners wrote a fresh narrative essay using AI edits and enhancing its flow assured cohesion.

The samples of writing were analyzed qualitatively against both post-intervention and pre-intervention essays to assess the extent to which learners had adopted AI feedback on their development.

Focus Group Discussions

Discussions with both learners and teachers focused on their experiences with using AI in the context of writing, including the challenges encountered and any observed improvements. Both groups shared accounts of moments that stood out—whether notably beneficial or concerning—particularly in relation to the feedback provided by AI tools.

Post-Focus Group Reflection Survey

Finally, insights pertaining to the impact of AI on writing improvement AI integration were discussed with the recommendation AI in classrooms for future incorporation.

Phase 5: Thematic Data Analysis and Interpretation

As this study adhered to qualitative methodology, theme-based analysis was performed to understand distinct roles of AI towards improving writing cohesion.

Student and Teacher Reflection Analyses:

Through focus group discussions, teacher reflections, and open-ended survey responses, the following themes were derived:

AI perceived benefits for writing cohesion enhancement.

AI-generated feedback utilization challenges.

Changes in writing confidence and organization strategies.

Writing Samples Analysis as a Case Study

AI-assisted feedback influence was analyzed through pre and post-intervention essay reflections in the context of:

Transitions and the logical flow of ideas.

- Overall progression in organizational structure and development of ideas.
- Student reflections on the impact of AI feedback on their writing. The absence of numerical paradigms in this case allowed for rich understanding towards the influence of AI tools on learners’ writing development processes, cohesion, and participant engagements.

Table 3.2 - Summary of the Timeline for Data Collection

Phase	Timeframe	Key Activities
Pre-Intervention Assessments	Last week of January- First week of February	Student & teacher surveys, collecting previous work documents for writing
Training Sessions	First week of February	AI ethics & Writerly training for learners and teachers
AI-Assisted Writing Implementation	From the second week of February to the second week of March	Learners use AI for writing while teachers observe and document their observations.
Post-Intervention Assessments	Third to Fourth week of March	Administered Post-Surveys to learners and teachers, collected writing samples after the intervention for analyzing reflexive writing.
Focus Groups & Qualitative Reflections	In the fourth week of March	Student and Teacher Focus Group Reflection.
Data Analysis & Interpretation	After data collection	thematic analysis , participants’ reflections and writing samples.

Summary

Cohesion in learners' writing is the core focus of this study. The researcher employed a qualitative approach to gain a better understanding as to how AI writing tools have an effect on cohesion in learners' writing, particularly the essays written by seventh and eighth graders in a private school in Lebanon. It is also aimed that as these tools are used, learners' writing skills will develop, especially in the organization of their essays. Qualitative methods were employed to do the research in as much depth as integration of learners and teacher's experiences and perceptions regarding AI writing tools.

The researcher also used focal groups of learners and teachers as a semi-structured interview for data collection. These strategies were aimed at obtaining complete, intricate and visual reports, which enabled the researcher to find out better how learners view and tackle the problem of cohesion in their writing and, particularly, how well AI is solving the problem. Moreover, educational purpose and context in which writing was supported with AI writing tools were elaborated through teacher interviews.

The researcher thoroughly examined the collected data from these qualitative methods through thematic analysis by seeking and discussing common features or themes with regard to cohesion in writing and AI tool's productivity. No ethical violations occurred at any stage protecting the privacy and consent of all respondents. Using this method, the aim of the study was to help appreciating the scope of AI in writing skill enhancement and to assist in shaping the educational system in Lebanon in the years to come.

3.9 Data Analysis

This part outlines the analysis techniques implemented on the qualitative data amassed through the research. The analysis intended to assess the impact of AI-assisted writing tools, particularly Writerly, on learners' writing cohesion and attempt to understand participant attitudes from before and after the intervention. The researcher undertook thematic analysis in conjunction with rubric and triangulation analyses to analyze the surveys, focus group discussions, writing samples, and AI feedback analyses.

Thematic Analysis of Survey and Focus Group Data

According to the Braun and Clarke (2006) six-phase thematic analysis model, the pre-and post-intervention student surveys and focus group sessions with the teachers were analyzed. It provided an organized method alongside the needed flexibility to focus on the findings as well as the participants' stories around specific themes or insights.

The first step from the process is familiarization. For this, all transcripts and survey answers were read in rounds to build context and internalize the words, phrases, and ideas that participants provided. Subsequently, initial codes had been created manually. Attention was paid to the identifications of having concerns around writing cohesion issues, the effectiveness of AI feedback, and perceptions of improvement or developing behaviors around writing. Some of the initial codes that were developed included Perceived Benefits of AI Feedback, Challenges in Adapting to AI, Teacher-Student Divergence in Perceptions, and Cognitive Engagement with Feedback.

Themes were developed and refined through iterative cycles to ensure they met the adequacy criteria of range, depth, and internal consistency, while remaining aligned with the study's

guiding research questions. The researcher further substantiated the findings by presenting them in a richly grounded narrative, incorporating direct quotations from participants to authentically represent the lived experiences of both learners and instructors involved in the study.

Comparative Analysis of Student Writing Samples

The analysis of student writing samples pre- and post-intervention was done using a systematic rubric integrating three key dimensions: cohesion - the use of coherent devices and logical connectors, organization- the arrangement of paragraphs, and clarity- reading level transitions between the sentences. The analysis showed there were improvements to writing quality.

Writing prior to intervention showed persistent problems as follows: poor advancement of ideas, poorly managed transitions, and sudden shifts into new paragraphs. Whereas, post-intervention writing indicated use of more sophisticated cohesive devices, better use of paragraph development, and more logical coherence. These changes were most apparent for those learners who used the AI-generated feedback. The analysis showed different and collective findings of how learners applied AI tools to practical writing within the classroom.

Examining Writerly Feedback Reports

As part of data capturing, the AI tool Writerly provided automated feedback reports during the entire intervention. These reports were useful in identifying what issues related to cohesion were most frequently flagged and how the learners responded to those flags, as well as what patterns of feedback emerged over time.

The analysis revealed that Writerly was especially concerned with the internal coherence of sentences, repetitive/recursive patterns within texts, and the overall clarity of structured

paragraphs. Importantly, there was variation in how all learners responded to this feedback ; for some, suggestions were ruthlessly taken up verbatim, while others engaged more selectively, revising using a blend of AI and teacher suggestions . Analysis across different groups revealed that learners who worked on their drafts in cycles and received feedback from AI tended to have a better overall structure and flow in their final drafts. This implies that the application of teacher oversight in addition to the AI instruction allowed learners to go beyond superficial application of the feedback offered and instead interact with the comments in an authentic way.

Triangulation for Credibility and Validity

In order to achieve validity, data was gathered from various sources, including surveys, interviews, writing samples, and reports from Writerly, and was cross-validated to corroborate the findings. This approach was beneficial for the researcher as it enabled them to look across datasets and combine results to identify consistent patterns, thus minimizing bias and overreliance on a single dataset.

As an example, survey responses from learners stating that AI tools helped improve their organization of ideas were backed by actual improvements seen in their writing samples as well as teacher observations. Moreover, comments from focus groups about AI-generated feedback being somewhat vague or impersonal were observed in writing samples with mechanical transitions or lack of stylistic voice. AI tools were suspected of wielding complex effects on writing development, and triangulation's methodological rigor deepened the interpretation.

Ensuring Trustworthiness of the Data

The researcher used different approaches in the study to ensure its findings were trustworthy. Focus group sessions provided an opportunity for member checking, which enhanced credibility

as participants could confirm the researcher's interpretation of their remarks. In detail documenting the coding, theme development, and operational steps taken in the study, dependability was achieved in preserving audit trails. Participants' quotes and feedback helped interpretations, which strengthened confirmability, and frequent reflexive journaling reduced the influence of the researcher bias.

The Lebanese private middle school that was selected as the setting for the study provided detailed background information alongside the participant's background data in order to improve transferability. With such rich descriptions, educators and researchers are positioned to make informed judgments about the applicability and relevance of the findings to different educational contexts.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the institution and received approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Lebanese International University, which confirmed that the research protocols adhered to ethical standards for studies involving human subjects. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants, including parental or guardian consent for minors under the age of eighteen. Participants were fully debriefed on the study's purpose, their role, and their right to withdraw at any point without penalty.

To safeguard participant privacy and ensure data confidentiality, all responses and writing samples were anonymized and assigned identification codes. Personally identifiable information was either removed or replaced with alternative identifiers. Access to the coded data was

restricted to the principal researcher. All electronic files were stored in password-protected folders, and physical documents were secured in a locked electronic cabinet.

The confidential and theoretical emotional risks were not present in any focus group or interview kept in reserved private spaces. The ethical concerns followed Çelebi et al. (2022), Israel (2014), and Flick (2018) regarding participation, anonymity, and the professional management of qualitative information. Throughout the entire qualitative research study, the ethics reflexively put the participants' rights and welfare as priority while remaining unbiased to the data.

Implications for Educational Policy, Instruction and Curriculum

The analysis of data seems to suggest that there are urgent concerns with regard to curriculum planning, instructional methods, and policy making in Lebanese education systems. The embedding of AI writing tools such as Writerly can greatly assist in supporting the learners' writing coherence development if used with teacher involvement and embedded in a suitable curricular scope. Such learners who are in middle school developing specialized advanced academic writing skill areas will gain most from the modern teaching techniques.

Concerning curriculum frameworks, this study demonstrates the possibility of enhancing cohesion, clarity, and logical thinking AI integrated feedback systems can add to writing programs. AI tools provide learners with feedback that they can use for instant editing and improvement through revisions that need to be done repeatedly. The study claims, AI feedback combined with proper guidance is instruction can be highly effective as both a support device and motivation for development in writing skills. Consequently, curricula in Lebanon need to

integrate automated evaluation tasks that are aligned with national educational outcomes and private school standards and flexibility for innovation.

From the point of view of a teaching approach, the research suggests the need for comprehensive technology professional development that prepares educators to not only utilize AI, but also assist learners in their active engagement with such technologies. In particular, there are several competencies teachers need to have. Some of them are being able to make sense of the comments from AI's feedback, supervising learners' ability to sort pertinent recommendations from non-helpful ones, and averting overreliance on technological devices to help enhance independent writing skills. As Dai and Wang (2021) contend, AI serves its purpose best when its feedback is purpose-driven and adaptive to student requirements. If not carefully managed, there is a danger that learners may shift into uncritically adopting support provided by artificial intelligence at the expense of their own expression.

Apart from this, the research contributes to policies aimed at guiding the use of technology in education. It aids in the design of purpose-driven interventions on the use of AI in Lebanese educational systems, especially in private schools, which are most likely to adapt educational innovations. The same author notes that the education of the future will demand a policy-enhanced AI application, one that would advocate for the AI integration in staff development budgets, educational technology allocation, and formulated teaching policy for the use of AI powered devices in the curricula. By embedding AI within pedagogical reasoning, schools cannot only facilitate the effective adoption of technologies, but also guarantee their longevity and suitability.

Furthermore, the study examined the pedagogical implications by considering the interplay between technology, student participation, and writing outcomes. As Xie and Zhang (2022) pointed out, motivation and learning outcomes can be enhanced through the purposeful use of digital tools. In this case, learners who worked with AI-enabled drafting systems not only improved their technical cohesion, but also began viewing writing as a recursive, reflective act. Of note, sociocultural realities such as the language of instruction, the dynamics of the teaching and learning relationship, and the pace of the curriculum need to be considered in the context of using AI tools in Lebanese classrooms. These determine the potential adaptability and usefulness of AI technologies for pedagogical and curriculum differentiation.

This study portrayed the use and interactions with AI technologies in the classroom towards understanding the value of these tools to instruction at the elementary level. As such, educators, educational decision makers, and curriculum designers intent on using technology in writing instruction devoid of pedagogical compromise stand to benefit from these insights. The researcher provided evidence in the study to warrant the use of AI technologies in education through a caring lens on the humanity of the learners so that technology complements, rather than dominates, the sophisticated mental and social actions involved in writing.

Conclusion

In this chapter, the researcher focused on the implications of AI writing applications on the coherence of writing for a sample of Grade 7 and 8 learners from a private school in Lebanon. The research followed an interpretivist philosophical approach and utilized inductive logic within a descriptive, non-experimental study design to assess the progression of learners' writing throughout the AI intervention. The nature of this research was qualitative, providing a thorough

examination of the writing processes and the contextual factors influencing them, which is deeper than what is possible with quantitative approaches.

This chapter began by outlining the profiles of the participants and explaining the rationale for selecting them through convenience sampling. While this sampling method does not allow for generalizability, it was appropriate for the purposes of this study, as the context was rich and particularistic. The chapter then detailed the data collection instruments, which included surveys, focus group discussions, and reports generated from AI feedback sessions conducted both before and after the intervention. These instruments were pilot-tested for relevance and clarity, and all ethical considerations—including informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, and secure data storage—were strictly followed.

Qualitative data analysis was conducted using Braun and Clarke’s six-phase model of thematic analysis, supported by manual coding techniques. This approach enabled the researcher to develop detailed themes related to writing development, the influence of AI-generated feedback, and the perceptions of both learners and teachers. Analysis of writing samples, evaluated using rubrics, revealed marked improvements in cohesion, structure, and overall clarity. Additionally, feedback reports generated by the AI tool *Writerly* validated the students’ revisions and demonstrated their active engagement with the system, affirming the tool’s instructional value.

However, it must be noted that the algorithm does the trivial alterations to the learners’ writing cohesion with AI tools faster than a more intricate teaching approach would take. This study’s implications, however, do not remain within a single classroom setting. They demonstrate how AI can integrate traditional pedagogy and technology into a single framework—and one that

deeply redefines curricular, instructional, and policy paradigms. Moreover, this study can help address the gap regarding AI's impact on literacies and the education transformation in the Middle East.

In conclusion, this analysis emphasizes the need of professionally integrating AI writing tools, stating how they can improve pupils' writing skills when used with instructional and policy frameworks. It seeks collective concern from teachers, scholars, and policy framers to develop a balanced educational environment that harnesses technology and human teaching, nurturing 21st century critical literacy competencies.

Chapter 4: Results and Analysis

4.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the outcomes of the inquiry examining the issues of writing cohesion among seventh and eighth grade learners, along with their teachers from a private Lebanese school, and evaluating the use of Writerly, an AI-powered writing assistant tool, in overcoming such issues. The researcher used a combination of Pre-Intervention Student Surveys, Post-Intervention Student Surveys, Focus Group Interviews, Writing Sample Analysis, and Teacher Observations to gather data. Each analysis contributes to the two research questions and the research outcomes that were designed for this study.

4.2 Research Questions and Expectations Guiding the Analysis

The researcher guided the study by the following research questions:

Research Questions

Research Question 1: How do teachers and learners of grades 7 and 8 perceive the challenges of writing cohesion in a private Lebanese school?

Research Question 2: To what extent do AI writing tools improve writing cohesion among grade 7 and 8 learners in a private Lebanese school compared to conventional methods?

Research expectations

This study was supported by the research expectations listed below:

Expectation 1: Both learners and teachers will pinpoint particular difficulties regarding achieving writing cohesion, emphasizing the gap between grammar focus and logical flow of ideas.

Expectation 2: AI writing tools will aid learners in employing cohesive devices and organizing their ideas logically and hierarchically in a manner conducive to flow.

Expectation 3: The perception learners have regarding writing, as well their engagement with the revision process, will be more positive with the integration of AI-powered feedback tools into the instruction process.

Expectation 4: Instructional designers will appreciate AI tools for their role as a complementary resource within a structured instructional framework, rather than viewing them as a replacement for teacher intervention.

The figure below illustrates the data collection and analysis process employed in this qualitative study.

Figure 4.1 : Data Collection Analysis flow – AI Writing Cohesion Study

4.3 Results

Result of the Pre-mid Student Intervention Survey: The survey showed some problems regarding the learners' writing habits and their AI writing tool awareness. Almost three quarters, approximately 72%, of the Grade 7 learners claimed that they used technology primarily for entertainment purposes. A Grade 7 student stated, "I only use my tablet to watch YouTube or play games. You don't need to write anywhere." Another admitted, "I just write what comes to my head. Connecting ideas is not something I think I need to do." Regarding the Grade 8 learners, the percentage of those who had ever used an AI application stood at 58%, but mostly in relation to searching for information and not improving writing skills. A Grade 8 student noted, "I used Google to check facts for science projects, but I never used it to improve my essays." There was a complete lack of confidence concerning writing's cohesion: 68% of learners indicated that they struggled with the smooth flow of ideas in different paragraphs. As one Grade 7 student remarked, "My sentences are good when they stand alone, but when I put them together, it feels very choppy." Another student admitted, "I know words like 'because' and 'therefore' but I don't know when to use them." About AI expectations, 45% of respondents claimed that they were skeptical due to expecting outputs that sound robotic.

An 8th grader stated, "I am concerned about AI making my essay sound strange or phony." Nonetheless, around thirty percent stated something along the lines of cautious optimism, such as in this quote: "Perhaps it can help me better organize my ideas if I don't know how." In summary, these findings reveal the fundamental challenge learners encountered in achieving smooth flowing writing and their ambiguous hopes regarding technology-enabled assistance.

The survey highlighted that around 72% of the respondents from Grade 7 predominantly utilized technology for entertainment purposes and class academic writing drafts on very minimal occasions. A good number mentioned difficulties in achieving cohesive writing, especially in the smooth flow of connecting ideas. Moreover, 58% of the respondents who were in Grade 8 admitted using AI applications mostly for information fetching instead of improving their writing skills. Attitudes towards AI applications were skeptical amongst the learners, as 45% of them cited the robotic nature of outputs produced by AI as a major criticism.

Figure 4.2 : Pre-mid Intervention Survey Results: Student Writing Habits and AI Awareness

Post-Intervention Student Survey Results

The implementation of Writerly into instruction was followed by a post-intervention student survey that indicated a shift in learners' perceptions and experiences relative to writing cohesion. A rather striking proportion of learners, approximately 58%, felt that they could now organize

their ideas in a hierarchical or sequential fashion. One Grade 8 student articulated, ‘Earlier, all my thoughts came as a flow in the form of writing and now I have to order the connections and phrase them before I write them.’ Another Grade 7 student commented, ‘I explain why things happen by using “because” and “as a result,” not just listing facts.’ That said, an important number, 52% of learners, indicated that Writerly helped them enhance their transitions and logical flow of their paragraphs.

On the other hand, approximately 30% of respondents reported that although the tool had suggestions, they still waited for guidance to know how and when to implement suggested changes appropriately. One grade 7 student: ‘Once Writerly put some ideas forward for me, I was not very confident they were suitable for my paragraph.’ A portion (18%) of the learners voiced concern about the formal transitions that were suggested by Writerly not fitting their style, especially in narrative assignments. An eighth-grade student noted, "I wanted my story to sound real but Writerly sometimes gave me words like 'hence' or 'thus' that were too formal.” Still, the sentiment expressed suggested greater engagement with cohesion, awareness of physical and logical sequencing, and enhanced overall structure, meeting one of the instructional goals of the intervention.

The survey conducted after the intervention showed noticeable changes in learners’ working experiences with writing cohesion and how they interacted with the AI tool. The key findings are illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 4.3 : Post- Intervention Student Reflections on Writing Cohesion and AI Feedback

As noted in figure 4.3 , a high proportion of learners (58%) claimed that their ability to organize their ideas hierarchically or sequentially improved, while 52% reported clearer transitions and enhanced flow within paragraphs. Nevertheless, 30% of participants were unable to apply AI feedback without the aid of a teacher. Some (18%) felt that the transitions provided by Writerly were overly formal, highlighting the disparity between what is automated and the reality of student voices—particularly in narrative writing. This relies heavily on teacher assistance to navigate AI feedback towards making the most impact in teaching their learners.

Figure 4.4 : Summary of Changes : Pre- and Post-Intervention

Writing Sample Analysis

From the review of the pre-intervention and post-intervention writing samples, learners showed varied outcomes based on their different levels of proficiency. According to the specific prompts given to each grade level, this section has two parts: Grade 7 (expository essays on causes and effects of pollution), and Grade 8 (narrative essays on overcoming a personal challenge).

Grade Seven Writing Sample Assessment (Pollution Essay)

The seventh grade learners were asked to write an expository essay on the causes and effects of pollution. Pre-intervention samples showed a lack of idea integration with regard to causal ordering, causal linking, and idea sequencing. Several post-intervention samples showcased marked improvement. In the case of one student, the writer tried to explain the causal chain from factories to illness with the sentence: “Factories make smoke. It goes in the air. People get sick.”

After Writerly, the student produced, “Factories release harmful smoke into the atmosphere, and as a result, people develop respiratory problems.” Another example of change from “Pollution is bad. As an example, I could take the sentence “it kills fish. It makes the water dirty” and rewrite them into a sentence such as “Pollution, particularly pollution from industrial waste, contaminates water sources and kills aquatic life, rendering the water unfit for human consumption.” While a different student who said: “Cars cause pollution.”

Factories cause pollution,” underwent the same transformation. “Trash causes pollution,” without interrelations was able to revise to, “The operation of factories, the driving of cars, and even improper waste disposal are actions increasingly undertaken by humans that contribute significantly to pollution.” Not all learners showed strong improvement, though. One weaker student maintained, “Pollution is everywhere. People do it. It is bad,” which makes clear that these learners likely benefit from more direct instructional guidance to complement the feedback provided by AI tools.

In comparison, a high-performing student's pre-intervention draft contained one paragraph and after intervention, he produced the sophisticated completion of “Pollution comes as a result of human neglect or carelessness and causes dire effects like global warming, health problems, and the annihilation of ecosystems.” This indicates that he mastered the cause-effect relations as well as cohesive sequencing. All of these examples indicate that Writerly facilitated growth for most learners with regard to logical organization and flow, even though some level of tailored intervention was still necessary for lower performing learners.

Analysis of Grade 8 Writing Sample (Narrative Essay)

For Grade 8, learners wrote narrative essays about an event in their lives where they experienced a challenge, which affected their self-esteem. The pre-intervention writing showed the beginning stages of a chronological order with clear reflective conclusions and transitions. Post-intervention, there was holistic improvement across the board in learners' apt detailing of events and use of transitions to guide the reader. "I was nervous. I had a speech. I forgot words. It was bad," changed to "I was nervous as I stood before the class to deliver my speech. Having forgotten my words, I gathered myself, and after mustering my courage, I was able to finish my speech successfully." Another narrative, "I tried out for the team. I didn't make it. I was sad," became, "When I tried out for the basketball team and did not succeed, I felt disappointed." I used that as motivation to practice harder and by the next season, I proudly earned a spot." A third student, who used to write abrupt and disjointed sentences like, "I failed my math test. I studied more." was also reframing their stories.

"I passed," evolved their narratives into, "I failed my math test, which was discouraging, but it made me study every day to ask for help, and I finally passed my next exam." However, one of the low-achieving learners with minimal scaffolding still submitted, "I had a bad day. It wasn't good. I got better later," demonstrating almost no narrative construction. On the other end of the spectrum, one advanced student with excellent integrated narration demonstrated exemplary growth from, "I was so nervous I felt sick. I froze and forgot all my lines," to, "Experiencing stage fright in the school play taught me that I'm not truly confident until I muster the courage to do things even when they scare me, which remains one of the most valuable lessons I learned." These outcomes highlight that for stronger learners, Writerly had a greater impact on the

scaffolded reflection and coherence at the personal level while chronological order had more impact on weaker learners.

Focus Group Analysis

The Focus Group Discussions demonstrated as learners reflected deeply about interacting with Writerly how it influenced their writing cohesion skills. Advanced learners had positive reflections and noticed that Writerly made them more aware of transitions and logical flow. An 8th grader once said, “I used to just write one event after the other, but now I try to think about how each event connects to the subsequent one.”

Additionally, a seventh grader noted, “Writerly showed me where I missed a cause and effect like when pollution happens and why.” Certain learners appreciated the ability to adjust their work based on feedback prior to finalizing their drafts. A Grade 7 participant noted, “It told me when my ideas were just listed and not connected, so I fixed it before giving it to my teacher.”

Less proficient learners did not find the tool as easy to use. One Grade 8 student cited their frustration by exclaiming, “Writerly gave me suggestions, but at times, the words it provided did not align with what I was trying to convey.” As another participant described potential issues of dependence, “Now I always check Writerly before finishing my work because I feel as though something important will be omitted if I do not check.” These conversations surfaced that although AI feedback was useful for increasing awareness of cohesion, it was inadequate for more sophisticated levels of writing improvement without teacher mediators—especially for learners with less developed skills.

Teacher Observations and Feedback

Educators noted the significant changes and trends in student writing at and after the intervention point with Writerly. Top-performing learners improved strikingly in idea order and linking paragraphs together. One of the English teachers noted, “The difference was remarkable – their writing began to flow with the appropriate phrases indicating ‘resulting in’ and ‘consequently’ connecting ideas together.” Teacher observations indicated that mid-level learners used the tool successfully but often needed scaffolded confirmation through conversation. A grade eight teacher explained, “Writerly guided them to better organizational skills but most needed me to tell them why certain transitions were more effective in their narratives.”

Weaker learners, on the other hand, tended to thoughtlessly apply AI recommendations. One of the teachers reflected, “Some learners just put in ‘thus’ or ‘furthermore’ without understanding what they were trying to communicate, so we had to go back to why flow makes sense in writing.” There was consensus among all teachers that Writerly was very good as an initial support tool, but that listening to and teaching learners is what educators needed to do. A Grade 7 teacher who said, “Writerly opened their eyes to the idea of coherence, but the teacher made it profound”, aptly captured this. Furthermore, some instructors reported worrying about dependency, pointing out that some learners started to over heavily rely on AI.

Summary of Findings and Triangulation Logic

The analysis of combined data from the surveys, writing samples, focus groups, and teacher observations provides an answer to the research questions in a systematic manner. Both teachers and learners recurrently noted cohesion in writing as one of the most significant challenge areas that confirms Research Question 1. Learners’ initial attempt at writing showed no comprehensive

application of transitions, logical progression, and unity within paragraphs. The Grade 7 and Grade 8 writing samples taken after the intervention demonstrated improvement in the application of cohesive devices and idea integration to some extent. In addition, consensus among teachers and focus group participants corroborated the finding that while AI tools enhanced surface cohesion, true cohesion at all levels was created only with adequate human engagement and thoughtful work. Learners who had better developed basic skills were more able to work independently with the support of Writerly, while others required more personalized support. Consequently, it can be concluded that the impact of AI was beneficial, but uneven and depending on the student's prior writing skills and ability to revise independently.

4.4 Triangulation of Qualitative Findings across Multiple Data Source

Using triangulation of qualitative sources, this study's results were synthesized. The diagram below shows the intersecting insights that were obtained.

Figure 4.5: Triangulation of Qualitative Findings across Multiple Data Source

The integration of data from student surveys, writing samples, focus group interviews, and teacher observation, as illustrated in Figure 4.5, identified central themes critical for responding to both research questions. The combined corroboration of these data sets strengthens the argument that AI feedback paired with systematic teacher intervention enhances the cohesion of learners' written output.

Critical Reflection: Differentiated Outcomes and Careful Consideration

The use of proprietary AI tools display the assistive features aimed at promoting synergy among constituents, for example, Writerly Positively impacts the construction of complex texts (Ohler & O'Neal 2023) but results remain varied based on learners' levels and their competencies with technology. In the case of high-performing learners, they were able to demonstrate continual improvement in maintaining a logical flow. On the other hand, middle-performing learners improved with moderate assistance. Unfortunately, low-performing learners were unable to meaningfully utilize AI assistance without extensive teacher guidance. This warns against the assumption that all diverse student populations benefit from the use of AI writing tools using a 'one-size-fits all' approach. Moreover, the results highlight the danger of overreliance on AI, especially in the absence of robust metacognitive revision skills, as learners may lack the necessary self-regulation to evaluate and manage their work. Thus, AI tools should only be regarded as supplemental resources rather than primary instruments designed to foster intricate writing abilities.

4.5 Summary of Key Findings

Both learners and teachers noted that maintaining coherence in writing remained a notable challenge.

As learners reported, taking part in the interventions enhanced the attention given to the narrative and logical flows of cohesion in both expository and narrative writing.

More advanced learners made better use of the AI-feedback tools than less advanced learners, who still needed a great deal of direct teacher support.

Teachers characterized Writerly as a functional instructional tool, however, they underscored its inability to replace the detail, explanation, guidance, and teaching that only other human educators can provide.

Attempting to reduce reliance on AI tools proved only partially effective. Nevertheless, the combination of survey results, writing samples, focus group, classroom observational data, and other writing tasks retrieved revealed that Writerly's capability to encourage the development of coherent writing independently across all ability levels was limited.

4.6 Evaluation of Research Expectations

To evaluate the results in relation to the scope of the study, the findings were analyzed in comparison to the expectations formulated at the beginning of the research study. The first expectation- the learners and the teachers would be able to identify specific challenges regarding writing cohesion- was completely satisfied. Both teachers and learners had clearly identifiable gaps regarding learners' abilities to construct flows logically, paragraph construction at the

macro-level, and gap utilization of transitional devices. This validates the major challenge, which was the focus of the study.

The second expectation, which was partially met, is that AI writing tools would assist learners in organizing their ideas hierarchically and logically. A number of learners using Writerly showed marked improvement in idea construction as well as text structuring; however, many the lower achieving learners still required considerable teacher support to apply the feedback in a meaningful way. This finding illustrates the point that AI support does not provide the level of assistance needed to foster cohesive writing skills to all ranges of learners.

The third expectation that learners' attitudes toward writing and revising would change for the better with the integration of AI feedback was already met---post-intervention surveys and focus groups showed learners significantly appreciated the revising stage, as well as the basic notion of linking the ideas logically within the text.

Lastly, the fourth expectation, which predicted that teachers would perceive AI tools in a supplementary role as opposed to a primary teaching role, was also fully met. Observations of teachers showed that Writerly was useful and offered prompt feedback; however, it did not replace the individualized, intricate guidance that classroom instruction entails.

As a whole, the research expectations were met largely. The results of the investigation sustain that AI tools for writing will assist in enhancing the cohesion of learners' writing; however, more thoughtful and flexible instructional plans are required to cater to the learners' ability levels on the use of AI feedback.

Conclusion

This chapter examined both learners' and teachers' perceptions of challenges related to writing cohesion and assessed the impact of the AI writing tool *Writerly* on the logic, flow, and cohesion within students' compositions. The findings indicated that most learners demonstrated improved coherence as a result of using *Writerly*. However, the tool's effectiveness was influenced by the level of direct teacher support provided and the individual learner's writing proficiency. These results suggest that technology, when integrated into structured and pedagogically sound lesson plans, can significantly enhance students' compositional skills across broader writing tasks. Building on these findings, the next chapter aims to interpret the results through the lens of relevant educational theories and frameworks, connect them to existing literature, and offer instructional design recommendations tailored to the Lebanese educational context. It also outlines the study's limitations and proposes directions for future research. The overarching goal of this study has been to develop a nuanced understanding of the role AI technologies play in shaping middle school students' cohesive written discourse within the broader context of teaching and learning processes.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Interpretation

5.1 Introduction

This chapter includes an evaluation of the Lebanese private school teachers and learners' perceptions concerning the challenges of writing cohesion. Furthermore, this study looked at the effects of the Writerly AI tool on learners' writing cohesion enhancement abilities. The discussion is situated within the bounds of the Lebanese English Language Curriculum for Cycle 3, which includes grade 7 and 8, where strong focus is given towards fostering the learners' ability to provide coherence and logical progression in their pieces of writing.

This chapter attempts to look at the findings in relation to the literature pertaining to the integration of Cognitive Constructivism and Sociocultural Theory with thematic analysis of different data sources such as surveys, focus groups, writing samples, and teachers' observations. These theories help explain the rationale behind selecting an AI tool focused on cohesive writing, and how such a system supports the development of cohesive written discourse. This chapter also discusses the educational implications of the findings, acknowledges the study's limitations, and outlines directions for future research.

The main focus of this chapter is to explore how artificial intelligence applications, especially Writerly, can be integrated into teaching frameworks to mitigate the increasing issues of writing coherence in Lebanon's education systems. It also attempts to bridge the gaps through analyzing the writing practices of learners and teachers and provides reasonable measures for joining AI technologies to the educational processes.

This work is designed to fill an apparent gap in scholarly work concerning the use of technology in education and teaching writing, especially in terms of the use of AI technologies in a context that is usually characterized by a dominant teacher-centered approach. The results provide an understanding of the benefits and drawbacks of AI writing tools concerning coherence while also highlighting the reluctance in accepting the need for the use of AI tools and the heavy dependence on educator's input and oversight.

5.2 Explanation of Findings Associated With Research Question 1: Perception of Challenges Relating to Writing Cohesion

The first research question looked into what Grade 7 and 8 learners and teachers understand as the challenges of achieving cohesion in writing, especially considering the sequencing and arrangement of ideas. Results showed that learners as well as teachers encountered considerable problems with the logical arrangement of ideas, transitions, and paragraph coherence.

Learners reported that they could get the components of a sentence together, but they faced the problem of weaving the sentences into a well-structured, logical piece of text. Many learners complained that they tend to “jump from one idea to another” and do not know how to organize their thoughts around a single main idea. This observation supports the theory of Cognitive Constructivism views learners as active agents in the construction of knowledge; however, it also emphasizes the need for a structured, step-by-step framework to support the mastery of complex cognitive tasks—such as organizing ideas into cohesive texts (Piaget, 1973).

Educators repeated these difficulties, saying how learners seemed to grasp the general grammar rules but lacked knowledge of more advanced discourse-level components such as cause-effect, contrast, and logical development within and between paragraphs. This reflects Vygotsky's

(1978) Sociocultural Theory that learning, being a social activity, requires learners to have more sophisticated social guidance to shift past shallow elements like grammar toward deeper skills such as writing cohesion. In particular regard of the Lebanese learners, they confront the issues between the expected curriculum boundaries and the implemented instructional practices.

These difficulties best fit Graham's (2019) theory that writing cohesion evolves over time and requires focused, organized instruction. In the same way, the National Center for Education Statistics (2012) noted that the majority of composition classes over-focus on teaching grammatical and syntactical issues at the expense of organizational skills, leading to incoherent writing. For this case study, the pre-intervention data showed that a significant number of learners were falling short of Lebanon's English Language Syllabus for Cycle 3 (CERD, 2020), in which the described learning outcome emphasizes "organizing ideas coherently in paragraphs and essays using appropriate connectors and sequencing devices." This disparity illustrates the need for an approach that integrates the instruction of grammar as a skill and the cognitive knowledge of text cohesion as a whole.

Furthermore, the teaching methods used at the school appeared to emphasize grammar and vocabulary teaching more than text organization and logical sequencing. While important, these aspects do not in themselves facilitate the advancement of integrated writing. As Sociocultural Theory notes, learners need more defined interaction with more knowledgeable peers and mentoring adults for effective cognitive growth in writing (Vygotsky, 1978). Thus, an instructional shift is needed to not only integrate precision into the curriculum, but also advanced organizational and cohesion-building skills.

5.3 Interpretation of Results Related to Research Question 2: The Consequences of AI Writing Tools on Cohesion

The second research question examined the impact of the Writerly AI tool on 7th and 8th grade learners' writing cohesion concerning their other forms of teaching. The findings revealed that Writerly AI greatly improved learners' writing flow regarding the logical progression of ideas between paragraphs, as well as paragraph level cohesion. Writing samples taken after the intervention showed learners used cohesive devices to logically organize ideas, chronological sequence events in narratives, and articulate clear cause-and-effect relationships within their texts.

The results are in line with Cognitive Constructivism theory, which states that learners integrate new information with existing knowledge. In this scenario, AI feedback helped learners identify gaps in the flow of their writing and offered suggestions for linking ideas in a more coherent manner. Nonetheless, the findings emphasized a disparity in how different learners leveraged the AI resource. For example, some learners who were more proficient at writing could seamlessly integrate the AI's recommendations into their drafts and did not rely on further guidance. This supports Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) where it is argued that learners are able to do tasks if given appropriate support (Vygotsky, 1978). While more autonomous learners were able to fully utilize the AI-generated feedback, less proficient writers struggled to construct cohesive narratives and required additional instructional support to effectively apply the AI's recommendations.

It's surprising that some learners did not make effective use of AI feedback. For example, they added transition phrases, but failed to think about how these lines blended with the rest of the

text. This supports Vandergriff (2016) and Mohammadreza & Safabakhsh (2021), who argued that unmoderated AI feedback weakly engages users and elicits superficial interactions with the text. As far as the Lebanese context is concerned, this is an issue because the curriculum places increasing sophisticated written demands on learners, including the logical sequencing of ideas (CERD, 2020).

The study does offer hope that tools like Writerly AI can motivate learners to work toward greater cohesion in their texts, even if that comes at a cost. Still, the results suggest that AI should not supplant direct instructional teaching. Rather, as Sociocultural Theory points out, AI is most useful when employed within a constructivist context where teachers actively facilitate learner environments in which feedback is thoughtfully applied (Vygotsky, 1978).

As mentioned before, utilizing tools like Writerly can improve the coherence of a written piece. Despite that, the findings of the study suggest that these resources must be integrated with more traditional methods of teaching if they are to be truly beneficial in aiding student development. This aligns with the Cognitive Constructivism perspective that states that learners engage in purposeful scaffolded reflection that is iterative with the writing, as well as Sociocultural Theory that emphasizes the learning that occurs through social interactions alongside necessary instructional scaffolding.

5.4 Discussion Based on Research Expectations:

This study was supported by the research expectations listed below, which guided the investigation into the challenges of writing cohesion and the role of AI tools in addressing these challenges:

Expectation 1: Both learners and teachers will pinpoint particular difficulties regarding achieving writing cohesion, emphasizing the gap between grammar focus and logical flow of ideas.

Expectation 2: AI writing tools will aid learners in employing cohesive devices and organizing their ideas logically and hierarchically in a manner conducive to flow.

Expectation 3: The perception learners have regarding writing, as well their engagement with the revision process, will be more positive with the integration of AI-powered feedback tools into the instruction process.

Expectation 4: Instructional designers will appreciate AI tools for their role as a complementary resource within a structured instructional framework, rather than viewing them as a replacement for teacher intervention.

Expectation 1: Identification of Challenges Regarding Writing Cohesion

The first research expectation was that learners and teachers would highlight particular challenges regarding writing cohesion, especially focusing on the gap between grammar and the flow of ideas. The findings from the study completed from this case were in full agreement with this expectation. Both learners and teachers noted difficulties in the logical sequencing of ideas at the movements, transition, and unity at the paragraph level. Learners frequently provided commentary of the sort that while they can create sentences, their ability to connect the sentences is another ball game all together.

These findings support Cognitive Constructivism (Piaget, 1973), which posits that understanding is constructed gradually through active engagement with tasks. In this context,

learners' difficulties with writing cohesion may be attributed to their current stage of cognitive development, which necessitates structured scaffolding to support the logical development and articulation of ideas in writing. Additionally, the Sociocultural Theory (Vygotsky, 1978) offers a complementary perspective, suggesting that writing challenges cannot be understood solely as cognitive limitations. From this viewpoint, the absence of sufficient instructional and peer-mediated interaction plays a critical role, as learners require social guidance and collaborative support to acquire these complex writing competencies.

Findings from the study suggest that the difference between grammar-based teaching and the ability to write clearly and in a well-organized manner is quite significant, which aligns with past literature (Graham, 2019; National Center for Education Statistics, 2012).

Expectation 2: AI Tools Enabling Cohesion and Organization Framework

The second expectation focused on the use of AI writing tools to support learners in employing cohesive devices and organizing ideas logically and hierarchically. This expectation was largely fulfilled, as the findings indicated that *Writerly* AI contributed to noticeable improvements in learners' writing organization and use of transitional elements. Students who engaged with the tool were able to self-correct issues related to flow and received prompts that helped them refine the sequence and structure of their ideas. These outcomes align with the principles of Cognitive Constructivism (Piaget, 1973), which posits that learners actively build and refine knowledge—in this case, of cohesive writing indicators—through feedback and engagement with meaningful tasks.

However, as the study also found, reliance on AI feedback is inadequate for all learners. As independent users of AI suggestions, proficient learners were able to integrate them, but struggling learners needed greater teacher support to enable the necessary changes. This corroborates Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) which suggests that some form of teacher scaffolding is necessary to help learners resolve their current inability to use AI feedback properly (Vygotsky, 1978). Consistent with other studies (Vandergriff, 2016; Mohammadreza & Safabakhsh, 2021), there is a lack of teacher direction accompanying the AI feedback that results in trivial alterations to be made. This reinforces the need for teachers to facilitate the AI revision process.

Expectation 3: Improving the Learners' Overall Attitude towards Writing and Revisions

The third expectation was that the AI-integrated tools would improve learners' perception-with respect to revising the writing and engaging with the writing in its different phases. This was only very partially fulfilled. Student attitudes towards writing seemed to improve because AI feedback made it simple to identify and repair cohesion gaps.

This shift aligns with Sociocultural Theory, which asserts that learning is a social process shaped by interactions with others and mediated through tools and resources, including technological ones (Vygotsky, 1978). AI tools, by offering immediate and personalized feedback, have supported learners in perceiving the writing process as more manageable and less intimidating. However, the study also revealed that students' attitudes toward writing were influenced by their prior digital experiences—a finding consistent with Cognitive Constructivism, which emphasizes that learning processes vary according to individuals' existing knowledge and experiences (Piaget, 1973).

Expectation 4: AI Should be Used as a Complementary Resource, Not a Substitution

The fourth expectation posited that instructional designers would value AI applications as complementary tools within an instructional framework, rather than as replacements for teacher involvement. This was confirmed by the study's findings, which showed that AI tools were most effective when integrated with teacher-led activities. Specifically, AI served as a supplementary resource that provided learners with real-time feedback on cohesion, while teachers addressed more complex issues, such as coherence at the discourse level. This reinforces the principle from Sociocultural Theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which emphasizes that technology should augment rather than replace human instruction. The effectiveness of AI tools depended largely on teachers' ability to scaffold learning by helping students interpret and apply AI-generated feedback to improve their writing in a focused and meaningful way.

Furthermore, the Standing Committee highlights that Cognitive Constructivism (Piaget, 1973) supports the use of AI to enhance active learning in well-structured lessons where constructivist principles are deliberately applied. In this view, teacher presence remains essential, as learners require guidance to engage meaningfully with AI feedback within developmentally appropriate instructional settings.

Figure 4.6 :Diagram showing the alignment between the research expectations and the actual findings of the study.

5.5 Connecting Outcomes with Relevant Literature

The outcomes of this research align with existing literature highlighting the persistent challenges of teaching writing cohesion in ESL contexts, as well as the growing potential of AI technologies to address these issues. Graham (2019) argued that writing instruction should move beyond what he referred to as “grammar gymnastics”—a narrow emphasis on sentence-level accuracy—and instead prioritize teaching learners how to connect ideas coherently within and across texts. The findings of this study affirm Graham’s assertion: while many Lebanese learners demonstrated the ability to construct grammatically correct sentences, they continued to struggle with cohesion at

the paragraph and text levels. Their compositions often lacked the structural glue needed to integrate ideas smoothly, resulting in fragmented and incoherent narratives.

Similar concerns were raised by the National Center for Education Statistics (2012), which reported that while many educational systems emphasized organizational structure, they lacked clarity in how content was effectively taught. This trend was evident in the pre-intervention data collected for this study, particularly from student surveys and focus group discussions. Learners frequently indicated that although they were taught to produce correct sentences, they had received little instruction on how to ensure logical progression and continuity of ideas across a text. Teachers echoed this sentiment, acknowledging that instructional time was often devoted to grammar in response to curriculum and exam pressures, leaving cohesion underemphasized in practice.

These instructional gaps are associated with Cognitive Constructivism. According to Piaget (1970), learners develop progressively from concrete to abstract thinking. Components of texts are coherent with one another at the sentence level and require higher-order skills like synthesis and analysis, which only develop through deliberate scaffolding. In cases where learners are trained to only write correct sentences without any form of encoding about relationships involving meanings, their cognitive development with regards to complex writing tasks stunts. Also, from a Sociocultural standpoint, the classroom as such, and some objects found therein, constitutes a mediating structure. When teachers have no strategies or resources to demonstrate cohesive writing, learners lack social mediation in their ZPD (Vygotsky, 1978).

The case study of Writerly exemplifies the usefulness and lack of AI-based tools at the same time. After engaging with the tool, learners tended to use transition phrases more often (e.g., “therefore,” “however”), which points to superficial gains. More frequently, learners did not logically sequence the arguments or reason them coherently. Their transitioning was done mechanically, raising the same doubts Mohammadreza and Safabakhsh (2022) put forth about AI tools leading learners to “algorithmic writing,” where learners follow directions without thinking due to a lack of feedback on inputs. The feedback loop becomes passive and non-reflective, superficial text becomes easier to produce, but will lack important reasoning or essential structure.

This shows the importance of monitored AI integration. Instruction should be enhanced with AI rather than AI replacing instruction wholly. Learners should learn to reflect on AI-generated feedback, question it, and make meaning-based—not merely surface-level correctness—decisions regarding structure. This is in alignment with the work of Choi & Park (2023) where they claim writing done with AI tools is most useful when embedded in activities promoting metacognitive awareness through teacher guidance, such as in peer review or collaborative revision processes.

Within the Lebanese curriculum, there is a specific aim with Cycle 3 learners to 'organize ideas in paragraphs and essays using appropriate connectors and sequencing devices properly.' (CERD 2020). Nonetheless, the study shows these curriculum expectations are not being met in a number of classrooms. There seems to be a gap between the outcome and the instructional practices of the teachers. The addition of AI tools such as Writerly, if paired with adequate teacher training and critique, could help close the gap between policy and practice. This,

however, needs to be carefully paced and sustained with longitudinal professional development that gives voice to educators explicitly teaching cohesion—modeling, guided writing, and sustained dialogic interaction.

A teacher might demonstrate a think-aloud where he models writing a paragraph explaining why particular transitions are chosen to enhance flow, rather than just assigning a writing task and letting AI provide feedback. Learners could subsequently work with Writerly in a guided writing station with the prompts, “Do these ideas logically follow one another?” and “Does this sentence support your paragraph’s main idea?” After using AI, learners can discuss in pairs changes with rationale, fostering engagement rather than mindless acceptance. This scaffolds the shift from mechanical writing to reflective, synthesized construction.

In a constructivist and sociocultural approach, this study's findings focus on cohesion in writing instruction as something that needs active teaching and support, not something to be facilitated passively. Used appropriately, AI is one strong mediating tool, but it must be coupled with strategic step-by-step teaching aimed at planning, thinking, talking, and learning for the student’s learning in order to master the material over time.

5.6 Implications for Teaching Practice

The findings from this research draw attention to the shortcomings and practices used to teach cohesive writing in Lebanese classrooms. More specifically, cohesion has to be redefined as a primary instructional goal rather than an ancillary objective to be dealt with after mastery of grammar and vocabulary. Currently, particularly in Cycle 3, writing instruction tends to emphasize sentence-level correctness, often neglecting important discourse-level features such as logical flow, idea advancement, and paragraph coherence. Nevertheless, grammatical accuracy

utterly devoid of the ability to logically connect ideas across a text becomes meaningless communication and therefore lacks meaning. Hence, this study insists on a pedagogical shift: cohesion must be taught deliberately, metacognitively, and contextually.

As stated by Cognitive Constructivism (Piaget, 1970), learners develop writing skills with integration of processes that build on previously obtained knowledge and active experimentation. Ideas of coherence and cohesion are higher-level skills that develop well after the learner has a firm grasp of basic grammatical skills. Teaching must also integrate systematic teaching of these concepts of abstract writing. For instance, some targeted short lessons could be offered once a week aimed at teaching the use of transitions, construction of cause-and-effect paragraphs, and paragraph unity. Teachers can give learners a passage that is logically disorganized and have learners reorder the sentences or revise the transitions, thus, promoting metacognition.

As Sociocultural Theory (Vygotsky, 1978) scholars remind us, learning, or in this case writing, is socially constructed and built with specific tools in hand through facilitated relationships in the ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development). In this view, AI writing tools like Writerly can function as scaffolds. These tools help learners revise independently by remaining within their ZPD. For example, the tools provide instant, targeted feedback on cohesion such as pointing out unclear transitions and suggesting better sentences to link together. On the contrary, learners without teacher guidance risk using AI suggestions uncritically. This poses a threat of writing becoming a mechanical exercise stripped of true coherence (Mohammadreza & Safabakhsh, 2022). Thus, it is emphasized that AI should not replace pedagogy but rather add upon it.

To encourage the active integration of AI into the classroom, the designing of AI-integrated writing tasks where the learners need to justify and reflect upon the changes made is essential.

For example, those learners who receive the cohesion-related feedback from Writerly can be asked to write brief annotations as to whether they accept the suggestion or not and why; this fosters metacognition and strengthens the sense of reasoning in their writing. Teachers may also put the learners into peer review teams where one student critiques and the other uses AI to edit and vice versa, embedding cohesion work deeper into the social-cognitive process.

Tackling these issues requires the collaboration of educators, the learners themselves, and even the instructional designers. The subsequent parts present specific considerations for each group.

Instructional Strategies Change for Educators- Integrated Writing Instruction:

Educators should integrate cohesion into the writing processes outcomes. Instructional focus should expand beyond sentence accuracy to include paragraph and text-level coherence.

Teachers should not wait to observe cohesion before grammar instruction. Teachers should build instruction around this skill and include it as a focus. For example, teachers can implement weekly mini-lessons on cohesive devices and structural patterns such as transition words, and pronouns, and even causation or contrast.

Within a lesson, learners can collaborate to revise model texts, reorder sentences, or create contextual transitions. Graham (2019) discovered that writing cohesion is a skill that develops with time, direct instruction, and practice. Also, the findings from this study show most Cycle 3 learners always struggle with a logical order of ideas which emphasizes the need for targeted cohesion instruction.

Feedback Using AI Tools:

Teachers should pair human feedback alongside AI to strengthen understanding. An instructor can help a learner navigate AI-driven insights and employ them within genuine writing

frameworks. As an example, after utilizing Draft Builder through Writerly AI, a teacher can prompt learners to offer group explanations of AI suggestions, which can then be shared with the whole class alongside feedback-driven discussions followed by structured revision sessions.

Learning Strategies Boosted Using AI Technologies for Learners

Fostering autonomy and reflection: Learners need to learn how to deal with AI critiques.

Learners have to be taught to analyze the recommendations and think about their actions instead of blindly going with AI's suggestions. Take, for example, the assignment of reflection logs where learners document the reasoning behind their acceptance or rejection of AI feedback and rationalize the acceptance or rejection.

Collaborative Writing Activities: Learners undertake collaborative scaffolding activities where peers support each other that corresponds well with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory.

Collaborative scaffolding aids in bridging the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), especially concerning the mastery of discourse level attributes. As an example, have learners work in pairs for peer editing where they analyze AI feedback against their own and their partners' revisions, debate cohesion techniques, and perform for the class.

Group Writing Together

Learners can gain from having activities that are peer supported which complies with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory. Social collaboration scaffolding helps fill in the zone of proximal development (ZPD), especially in achieving discourse-level features mastery. For example, put learners in pairs for editing tasks where they analyze AI critiques alongside their own and their partner's self-assessments, review mutual coherence, and give cohesive presentations of the final drafts to the entire class.

Strategies for Designing Instructions for Stakeholders Incorporating AI in Curriculum

Creation:

Writers' tools, such as Writerly, are best used in relation to goals set for instruction. Therefore, they should be integrated into the pre-writing, drafting, and revision stages of the sessions. For instance, designers can create unit plans in which learners work with AI during several revision cycles, each with specific cohesion skill prompts. Accompanying worksheets could have learners graphed AI outputs as worksheets where they had to fix cohesion errors based on the directions given.

Curriculum Development: Curriculum designers need to rework the English language syllabus for teaching writing skills to ensure cohesion is taught in clear alignment with grammar and vocabulary from the very beginning. As a result, the syllabus could facilitate weekly exercises dedicated to cohesion along with setting criteria for AI feedback in the editing process. This study found that learners, in the absence of designated teaching on cohesion, tend to fall short of the expectations set by the curriculum, thus needing reform that focuses on writing cohesion which constrains curriculum composition flexibility.

Sharpening Writing Instructional Skills Using Technology: For the effective use of AI tools, educational technology professionals and school leaders need to design specific training sessions intended to AI pedagogical scaffolding for the professional guidance of teachers. Teachers can be trained in using AI tools such as Writerly for constructive collaborative writing tasks for learners so that learners can write better, not just individually, but as a team. The application of technology in the classroom is most powerful when educators are equipped to use it as a means

of strengthening established practices, rather than removing them (Mohammadreza & Safabakhsh, 2022).

Addressing Varied Learning Environments: The instructional aid could be most useful in under-resourced or high-need classrooms where teacher support is scarce. AI can address learning gaps, skill gaps, and access gaps, but instruction must also address gaps in digital literacy for engagement, and offer alternatives for interfacing with feedback. For example, rural or low-income schools could be provided with low-bandwidth aids such as cohesion guides that are pseudo-AI-generated but printed. These guides can be paired with voice and video explanations delivered in Arabic or French to enhance guided learning.

Nevertheless, it emphasizes that private school learners were able to use AI tools and teacher support, which suggests adaptable frameworks like these could reduce equity gaps in Lebanese education.

Connecting the findings to Cognitive Constructivism and Sociocultural Theory reveals that AI applications such as Writerly might assist with coherence, but their utility, like all technological tools, is context-dependent. They should complement—not take the place of—direct instruction. These technologies, along with appropriate teacher scaffolding and collaborative instruction, can help learners build deeper cohesion in their writing. The study also emphasizes that AI-generated feedback is only useful within the context of a more complex learning activity that demands student initiative and active participation with the teacher’s structured support. Therefore, the teaching recommendations are predicated on the thoughtful use of AI in ways which afford learners the respect they need as social and cognitive beings.

Using AI Tools to Teach Writing Cohesion: Classroom-Based Implications

Mini-Lessons on Cohesive Devices with AI Integration for Speech Feedback : Writers can be assigned specific cohesive devices like blend, operative words and logical fragments, so they can practice writing with the help of AI Writerly. As learners draft, they receive immediate AI feedback on the transitions and organization of paragraphs reinforcing the concepts of the mini-lesson. That is, after teaching contrastive connectors like “however” and “although,” learners can be given a writing task where the AI is tasked to improve the writing cohesion using those structures.

Guided AI Prompts Peer Review in Google Docs

Teachers can supervise learners collaborating and conducting peer review through Google Docs. Every peer reviewer is expected to implement AI provided prompts such as “Place a more direct transition here” as they assess their partner's work. These interactions promote social learning (sociocultural theory) and promote metacognitive awareness. Teachers can scaffold by providing a list of cohesion markers as anchor points and encouraging the checklist to draw AI comments for each point made.

Cohesion-Centric AI Reflection Log Writing Portfolios

To encourage self-regulation and reinforce cohesion as a developmental skill, learners are required to digitally submit drafts of their portfolios, which AI-enhances over the term with suggested edits. Through each iteration, learners write self-reflections explaining what cohesive improvements the AI-blended suggestions entailed and detailing their learning outcomes from the implementation process.

Scaffolded AI Feedback for Struggling Learners

Tailored instructional strategies utilizing AI can be designed around the needs of weak cohesion writers. For instance, a student who has difficulty with paragraph-to-paragraph transitions might be provided an AI tool like *Writerly* or *QuillBot* where they learn to discover the gaps that need to be filled. The AI then guides them through a rewrite with provided sentence frames. This strategy promotes focused gap filling while enabling monitoring without undue burden on the student.

5.7 Limitations of the Study

Although this study explored the use of the AI writing tool *Writerly* and its potential to address cohesion-related challenges in Lebanese classrooms, several important considerations remain. The limitations that frame this specific context also open avenues for further inquiry, raising questions that future research could explore to deepen and broaden the understanding of AI's role in writing instruction.

The Limited Scope of the Sample: The examination strengthens the findings while also leaving out several factors, including the focus on only one private Lebanese school. This serves as the increasing scope that can be applied. This was however public and rural schools as well as those catering to pupils from different socio economic and ethnic backgrounds. Private school pupils in Lebanon seem to have greater digital resource access, courtesy of advanced technology and internet access, in comparison to public and rural school pupils who may be disengaged technologically due to device scarcity and low literacy training. Furthermore, the state of technological resources among various schools can yield different results when AI-based systems are employed. Thus, the conclusions drawn because of this investigation were entirely

limited to the region under observation and a more representative sample would serve to augment the research on the various other avenues uncovered.

Limitation in Scope Time Frame of the Intervention:

One significant limitation of this study was the relatively short duration of the intervention. The focus on writing cohesion was addressed over just a few weeks, which may not have provided sufficient time for learners to demonstrate meaningful or sustained improvement in this complex skill. As Graham (2019) notes, achieving coherence and cohesion in writing is a multifaceted cognitive process that requires sustained instruction and practice. Although the results showed signs of progress, the limited timeframe raises questions about the long-term impact and retention of these gains.

Developing the ability to write cohesive texts is a gradual process that cannot be fully realized in a brief intervention. Future research should adopt a longitudinal approach—spanning an entire academic year or more—in order to thoroughly assess the effectiveness of AI tools in promoting cohesion and supporting lasting learning outcomes. Without such an extended timeframe, it becomes difficult to evaluate the true potential of AI technologies in supporting the development and retention of writing skills over time.

Potential Bias in Self-Reported Data: Drawing on data from focus groups and surveys relies heavily on self-reporting, which in and of itself, presents an issue of its own. With the recent adoption of the AI writing tool, learners and teachers alike might have been attempting to respond in a manner that was socially acceptable or aligned with the cognitive appraisal theory of preference-consistent evaluation. As a result, the users might have been reporting perceived

effectiveness rather than actual effectiveness when it came to Writerly. Self-assessment data is useful when one aims to capture lived experiences; however, it can dilute the more concrete findings. To enhance the credibility of future investigation, mixed approaches to measuring cohesion that include a defined unit of assessment, such as benchmarks in composition testing or automated writing test with cohesion measurement software, should be utilized. This would mitigate bias and sufficiently describe the impact of the tool.

Lack of Advanced Rhetorical Reflection : This study focused on basic cohesion, such as transitions and paragraph unity, but did not address multilevel concerns especially important for mastering advanced academic writing skills. Audience considerations, tone, and voice development were left out. The aspects of writing listed above are essential for educational attainment and cultivating well developed arguments (Swales & Feak, 2012). Cohesion of a text in a single document is not adequate. It must be integrated with other skills if one is to create powerful academic prose. The Writerly tool, as tested in this study, helped with structural aspects of the texts but did not address more complex rhetorical elements. These other higher-order writing skills need to be looked into alongside AI design to assist learners with strategies for holistic writing.

Limited Examination of the Sociocultural Context: This study did not explore in sufficient depth the sociocultural context in which learners engaged with the AI tool. In Lebanon, classroom environments are often dominated by teacher-centered instruction, which can lead to resistance toward the adoption of educational technologies. Learners' responses to AI-generated feedback are likely influenced by broader cultural attitudes toward technology, instructional authority, and pedagogical norms. For instance, in classrooms where the teacher is regarded as

the primary source of knowledge, students may be hesitant to trust or act upon AI feedback unless it is explicitly endorsed by the teacher. Additionally, a general lack of interest or familiarity with technology—especially in more traditional academic settings—may undermine learners' perceptions of AI tools as credible and effective learning resources.

These contextual factors are important to consider when interpreting the findings and should be explored more thoroughly in future research, particularly in studies involving learners from diverse educational and cultural backgrounds. While this study offers valuable insights into the use of AI-supported tools like *Writerly* to improve writing cohesion, the identified gaps highlight the need for sustained, systematic investigation across varied educational contexts. A deeper understanding of sociocultural dynamics, combined with longitudinal studies and culturally responsive evaluative frameworks, will be essential to fully capture the potential and limitations of AI technologies in writing instruction and to extend the relevance of findings to broader educational settings.

5.8 Further Research Suggestions

This study has shed light on the complexities of writing cohesion issues and the potential impact of *Writerly* AI tools within a private school in Lebanon. However, there remain considerable gaps that require investigation, especially frameworks capable of shaping Lebanon's educational policies and school-based pedagogical approaches.

First of all, the effects of AI writing tools on writers' cohesion skills should be measured over several academic years. Since cohesion is a more sophisticated writing skill that develops gradually, it is reasonable to assume that the short-term gains identified in this study may not

result in increased levels of sustained writing cohesion in the long term. Understanding the degree to which AI-assisted writing improves the persistence of skills developed in English Language Learning during the Cycle 3 curriculum framework would be enhanced by tracking cohorts from Grades 7, 8, and 9.

Moreover, public and rural institutions of higher learning in Lebanon have yet to adopt AI tech into their academic frameworks. These schools ought to be analyzed for the impact AI accessories could have within under-resourced systems. The research would determine if employing AI tools for teaching writing would mitigate some inequities with Technological Educational Inequities and assist in narrowing rural-urban divides among learners in Lebanon's education system.

In addition, measuring the impact of AI technologies on learners' writing instruction performance versus technology-less instruction delivered by a lecturer would strengthen gaps in the literature. This would help determine whether the advantages offered by Writerly emanate from it being a digital device, the immediate feedback offered, or heightened attention on cohesion marking. This would enable English Language instructors to make AI-guided decisions regarding the strategic integration of technology into English courses while advancing the argument on the need to enrich traditional approaches for curriculum developers and policymakers in Lebanon.

Additionally, one should evaluate how AI-based writing applications can be implemented into the pre-existing Lebanese curriculum systems. Together with the Ministry of Education, some pilot study initiatives could be formulated to evaluate the... where AI systems could provide feedback without overriding the human instructing aides. Evaluation of the effectiveness of such

blended models would be beneficial to inform comprehensive national educational reform frameworks aimed at developing student's writing competencies to be undertaken later.

Moreover, some sociocultural research needs to be done to assess how Lebanese learners view writing, technology, and authority in relation to AI feedback interfaces. Lebanon, with its conservative teacher-dominated hierarchical educational system, may have learners respond differently to automated self-feedback tools compared to learners from more collectivist cultures. This type of socio-cultural context may help educators develop pedagogic and geographic AI writing aid programs for Lebanon.

Exploring learners' interactions with AI for instructional purposes—and how AI influences their creative, argumentative, and practical communication writing skills, beyond traditional academic writing—represents a valuable area for future research. This focus is especially relevant to the English language curriculum in Lebanese middle schools, which seeks to integrate 21st-century skills such as critical reasoning, originality, and digital literacy. Gaining insight into how AI supports various writing genres can broaden our understanding of its educational potential and application across diverse learning contexts.

Addressing the current gap in research regarding AI educational technologies within Lebanon's sociolinguistic, cognitive, and cultural dimensions—particularly in light of evolving global education frameworks—can help inform future policy and practice. A deeper, context-sensitive understanding of AI's role in education could support the development of policies that recognize AI as a multidisciplinary tool. Such insights would empower educators, researchers, and

policymakers to harness AI technologies more effectively in the design and delivery of instruction.

Conclusion

This research aimed to analyze the issues that learners as well as teachers face in writing cohesion while also looking into how the AI writing tool Writerly assists in logical flow, transition, and paragraphing. The results pointed out that despite the attempts made in the Lebanese English Language Curriculum for Cycle 3, a considerable number of learners are still having problems in the construction of ideas and paragraphs, and more so when the use of cohesive devices is involved. These challenges are worsened by gaps in learners' ability to structure ideas step-by-step and masterfully combine the ideas in their writing. While feedback provided by Writerly is useful, especially in relation to text synthesis, the usefulness of these tools was found to differ greatly between learners. Learners who were more self-sufficient in working with AI feedback tended to improve. Those who required more instructional support, in contrast, tended to struggle with using the tool. This study highlights the challenge of using technological aids in the classroom where they are not meant to supplant the teacher's role.

For learners requiring more detailed guidance, the use of AI technologies, such as Writerly, may create situations where learners become too dependent on automated systems for context—removing the contextual feedback a teacher would provide. This limitation strengthens the argument concerning the need for balanced integration of AI technologies in the classroom and the intelligence that assists, not replaces, teacher-student interactions with classroom synergy.

This study focused on Lebanon's education system, which helps address the gap in research on writing instruction and educational technology in the Middle East. This study illustrates the

extent to which modern technology can enhance—but not replace—teaching. One major conclusion from the study is that in Lebanon’s controlled environment dominated by conventional teaching practices, there is scope for reformative shifts in the educational landscape. The use of AI technologies in teaching writing should be accompanied by direct instruction so that the automated systems help streamline, rather than complicate, the holistic instruction of writing skills. This research is supportive of the blended approach to instruction where AI feedback systems are used in conjunction with direct teaching methods.

However, teachers leveraging AI can scaffold personalized feedback as learners engage with level-of-processing writing tasks involving greater cognitive demands such as overarching cohesion and structural considerations.

The study also emphasizes the importance of professional training for teachers, enabling them to engage constructively with AI technologies within pedagogical contexts that align with curricular goals and instructional frameworks. When provided with adequate training, teachers can adopt appropriate strategies to ensure that AI tools function as effective supports—rather than distractions—in the writing process. The model proposed in this study positions Lebanon as a potential leader in the development of culturally responsive and academically rigorous writing education systems. By thoughtfully integrating modern AI technologies into pedagogical practices, Lebanese educators can promote critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills among learners.

As global education increasingly embraces a blended model of in-person and online learning, Lebanon holds a distinctive advantage in harmonizing tradition with innovation. With the right

policy initiatives focused on research, technological infrastructure, and educational leadership, the country can move beyond basic literacy instruction and toward cultivating articulate, analytical, and creative 21st-century thinkers.

Appendices

Appendix A

Appendix A|: SPSS Principal Consent Form

Addressed to: Principal of Students' Paradise Secondary School

My name is Abir Sawan, and I am a graduate student at the Lebanese International University, Beirut Campus. I am pursuing a Master's degree in Education with a focus on Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL). My student ID is 12220034, and my expected graduation date is June 2025.

I am writing to seek your consent to conduct a study at Students' Paradise Secondary School (SPSS) as part of my final thesis. This study aims to investigate the impact of AI writing tools on the cohesion of writing among seventh and 8th-grade students.

Upon your approval, I would like to involve approximately 70 students from the specified grades. They will be asked to participate in a series of activities, including:

- Completing a pre-intervention questionnaire regarding their experiences with AI writing tools.
- Participating in semi-structured interviews before and after the intervention period.
- Providing writing samples during and after the intervention, using AI tools to assist with their writing tasks.

Participation in this study will be entirely voluntary, and students will have the right to withdraw at any time. I assure you that no personal information will be shared, and all data will be treated with strict confidentiality.

The results of this study will be used solely for academic purposes and will not be disclosed in any identifiable manner.

If you have any questions or require further information, please feel free to contact me via email at 12220034@students.liu.edu.lb

Please sign below to indicate your consent to the study as outlined above:

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix B: Students' Participation Form

Addressed to students of 7th and 8th Grades at Students' Paradise Secondary School:

Dear students,

I am currently working on my thesis in my final semester before obtaining my Master's degree in Education, focusing on Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL). To explore the impact of AI writing tools on the cohesion of your writing, I invite you to participate in this study by completing two questionnaires and providing writing samples during the intervention period. Your input will be invaluable in reaching the intended goals of my research.

Please note that your participation is voluntary. You are not required to participate, but your involvement will significantly contribute to the study I am conducting here at school.

If you are willing to participate, please sign this form. I am available for any questions you may have.

Name and Grade Level: _____

Date: _____

Signature: _____

Appendix C- Student Survey

Pre-Intervention Questionnaire (Student survey)

Thank you for participating in this study! This questionnaire is intended to understand your initial thoughts and experiences with AI writing tools before the intervention. Please answer honestly; your responses are confidential and valuable to our research.

Demographic Questions

1. **Grade level:**

Mark only one oval.

Grade 7

Grade 8

2. How often do you use AI tools for writing (e.g., Grammarly, ChatGPT, etc.)?

Mark only one oval.

Daily

Several times a week

Once a week

Rarely

Never

Student Perceptions of AI Writing Tools

In this section, we seek your thoughts on how AI writing tools affect your writing process. Your honest responses will help us understand their impact on organizing ideas and improving your writing.

3. To what extent do you feel that AI tools help with organizing your ideas?

Mark only one oval.

Not at all

Option 2

A little

Somewhat

A lot

Very much

4. How confident are you in using AI tools to improve your writing?

Mark only one oval.

Not confident

Slightly confident

Moderately confident

Very confident

Extremely confident

Open Reflections on AI Writing Tools

5. In your own words, describe how AI tools currently impact your writing organization

6. What do you find most challenging or helpful about using AI tools for writing?

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdjKzg154ADMTWDxNEkezRSMtCz4Okm-iAquod_E8jPM4sCpQ/viewform?usp=pp_url

Appendix D- Student Survey

Post -Intervention Questionnaire (Student Survey)

Thank you for completing this questionnaire! Now that you've used AI writing tools more extensively, please share how your perceptions and experiences may have changed. Your honest feedback is essential and will be kept confidential.

Indicates required question

Demographic Questions

1. Grade Level

Mark only one oval.

Grade 7

Grade 8

2. How often did you use AI tools for writing during the study period?

Mark only one oval.

Daily

Several times a week

Once a week

Rarely

Never

Student Perceptions of AI Writing Tools

3. How confident are you now in using AI tools to improve your writing?

Mark only one oval.

Not confident

Slightly confident

Moderately confident

Very confident

Extremely confident

4. To what extent do you feel that AI tools now help with organizing your ideas?

Mark only one oval.

Not at all

A little

Somewhat

A lot

Very much

5. Overall, how would you rate the impact of AI tools on your writing cohesion and organization since the study began?

Mark only one oval.

Very negative

Somewhat negative

Neutral

Somewhat positive

Very positive

Open Reflections on AI Writing Tools

6. Have you noticed any changes in your writing organization after using AI tools during this study? Please explain.

7. Can you describe any specific examples where AI tools helped or hindered your ability to organize and connect ideas in writing?

8. What do you think could improve your experience using AI tools for writing in the future?

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf15gJ7LJ>

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Appendix E – Teacher Survey

Pre-Intervention Questionnaire for Teachers

Thank you for participating in this study! This questionnaire is intended to capture your initial observations and perceptions regarding students' use of AI writing tools and how it may impact their writing cohesion and organization. Your responses are confidential and vital to our research.

Indicates required question

Demographic Questions

1. Grade Levels You Teach

Mark only one oval.

Grade 7

Grade 8

Both

2. How frequently do you notice students using AI tools for their writing assignments?

Mark only one oval.

Daily

Several times a week

Once a week

Rarely

Never

3. To what extent do you feel that AI tools currently help students organize their ideas in writing?

Mark only one oval.

Not at all

A little

Somewhat

A lot

Very much

4. How effective do you think AI tools are in assisting students with improving their writing cohesion?

Mark only one oval.

Not effective

Slightly effective

Moderately effective

Very effective

Extremely effective

Open Reflections on AI Writing Tools

5. In your experience, how do AI tools impact students' ability to organize and connect ideas in their writing?
6. What challenges or benefits have you observed in students' use of AI tools for writing?

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Appendix F – Teacher Survey

Post-Intervention Questionnaire for Teachers

Thank you for completing this follow-up questionnaire! Now that students have used AI writing tools more frequently during the study, please share any observed changes in their writing organization and cohesion. Your honest feedback is essential and ~~will be kept~~ confidential.

Indicates required question

Demographic Questions

1. Grade Levels You Teach ~~Untitled~~

Mark only one oval.

Grade Grade 8 both

2. How often did you observe students using AI tools for writing during the ~~study period?~~

Mark only one oval.

Daily

Several times Once a week

Rarely

~~never~~

Teacher Perceptions of AI Writing Tools

In this section, please share your views on how AI writing tools ~~impact~~ students' writing skills, particularly in organizing ideas and improving cohesion. Your insights will help us understand the tools' role in student learning.

3. To what extent do you feel that AI tools now help students with organizing their ideas in writing?

Mark only one oval.

Not at all

~~a little~~

~~somewhat~~

a lot

~~very much~~

4. Overall, how would you rate the impact of AI tools on students' writing cohesion and organization since the study began?

Mark only one oval.

Very negative

Somewhat negative

Neutral

Somewhat positive

Very positive

Open Reflections on AI Writing Tools

5. Have you observed any specific changes in students' writing cohesion or organization after increased use of AI tools? Please explain.

6. Can you provide examples where AI tools either supported or hindered students' ability to organize and connect ideas in their writing?

7. What improvements or adjustments would you suggest for better integrating AI tools in students' writing instruction?

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Appendix G

Grade 7 - Pre-AI Intervention Writing Sample: Causes and Effects of Pollution

Thank you for participating in this study! This form is part of a qualitative research project assessing the impact of AI tools on writing cohesion and organization. Please use the following rubric to evaluate the student's writing.

Indicates required question

Untitled Section

Writing Prompt for Student Submission

1. Write an expository essay on the causes and effects of pollution. Explain what contributes to pollution and its impact on the environment. Organize your ideas into clear paragraphs with an introduction, body, and conclusion.

Rubric for Teacher Evaluation

Cohesion: Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample..

1 = Needs Improvement: Transitions are lacking or unclear; ideas are poorly connected, making the text difficult to follow.

2 = Good: Some transitions are used, but connections between ideas may be awkward or insufficient, leading to minor confusion.

3 = Very Good: Ideas flow logically with appropriate transitions, demonstrating good organization and connection.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are seamlessly connected with excellent use of transitions, resulting in clear and engaging writing.

2. Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Coherence: Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

1 = Needs Improvement: Ideas are unclear and poorly organized; difficult to understand the main point.

2 = Good: Some clarity, but organization is inconsistent; the main point may be obscured by less relevant details.

3 = Very Good: Ideas are mostly clear and organized, with a logical progression that supports understanding.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are very clear and well-organized; the writing presents a strong, coherent message that is easy to follow.

3. Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Clarity and Development: Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

1 = Needs Improvement: Lacks clarity and detail; ideas are underdeveloped and difficult to understand.

2 = Good: Ideas are somewhat clear, but supporting details are limited or not fully developed.

3 = Very Good: Ideas are clear with adequate supporting details that enhance understanding.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are clear and well-developed; supporting details are relevant, thorough, and effectively enhance the main points.

4. Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Qualitative Reflection Questions

This section collects teachers' insights on the organization, cohesion, and clarity of the student's writing sample. Feedback will highlight strengths and areas for improvement prior to the intervention.

5. Describe how the student organizes and connects their ideas in this writing sample.
6. What specific strengths or areas for improvement do you notice in the student's writing?
7. How effectively does the student use transitions to enhance cohesion?

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Appendix H

Grade 7 - Post AI Intervention Writing Sample: Causes and Effects of Pollution

Writing Prompt

Writing Prompt for Student Submission

1. Write an expository essay on the causes and effects of one kind of pollution. Explain what contributes to this pollution and its impact on the environment. Organize your ideas into clear paragraphs with an introduction, body, and conclusion.

Rubric for Teacher Evaluation

Cohesion- Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample..

1 = Needs Improvement: Transitions are lacking or unclear; ideas are poorly connected, making the text difficult to follow.

2 = Good: Some transitions are used, but connections between ideas may be awkward or insufficient, leading to minor confusion.

3 = Very Good: Ideas flow logically with appropriate transitions, demonstrating good organization and connection.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are seamlessly connected with excellent use of transitions, resulting in clear and engaging writing.

2. Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Coherence: Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

1 = Needs Improvement: Ideas are unclear and poorly organized; difficult to understand the main point.

2 = Good: Some clarity, but organization is inconsistent; the main point may be obscured by less relevant details.

3 = Very Good: Ideas are mostly clear and organized, with a logical progression that supports understanding.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are very clear and well-organized; the writing presents a strong, coherent message that is easy to follow.

3. Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Clarity and Development: Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

1 = Needs Improvement: Lacks clarity and detail; ideas are underdeveloped and difficult to understand.

2 = Good: Ideas are somewhat clear, but supporting details are limited or not fully developed.

3 = Very Good: Ideas are clear with adequate supporting details that enhance understanding.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are clear and well-developed; supporting details are relevant, thorough, and effectively enhance the main points.

4. Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Qualitative Reflection Questions

This section collects teachers' insights on the organization, cohesion, and clarity of the student's writing sample. Feedback will highlight strengths and areas for improvement prior to the intervention.

5. Describe how the student organizes and connects their ideas in this writing sample.
6. What specific strengths or areas for improvement do you notice in the student's writing?
7. How effectively does the student use transitions to enhance cohesion?
8. What impact do you think the use of AI tools had on this writing sample?
9. Were there any notable improvements or regressions compared to previous writing samples?
10. How well does the student convey their main idea or argument throughout the piece?

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Appendix I

Grade 8 - Pre-AI Intervention Writing - Sample: Narrative

Thank you for participating in this study! This form is part of a qualitative research project assessing the impact of AI tools on writing cohesion and organization. Please use the following rubric to evaluate the student's writing.

Writing Prompt for Student Submission

1. In a narrative essay, recount an event when you faced a challenge that tested your self-confidence. Describe the situation and what made it difficult for you. How did you feel during this time? Explain how you worked to overcome the challenge and what you learned from the experience. Be sure to include details about your thoughts and feelings to make your story engaging.

Rubric for Teacher Evaluation

Cohesion- Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample..

1 = Needs Improvement: Transitions are lacking or unclear; ideas are poorly connected, making the text difficult to follow.

2 = Good: Some transitions are used, but connections between ideas may be awkward or insufficient, leading to minor confusion.

3 = Very Good: Ideas flow logically with appropriate transitions, demonstrating good organization and connection.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are seamlessly connected with excellent use of transitions, resulting in clear and engaging writing.

2. Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample.
Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Coherence: Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

1 = Needs Improvement: Ideas are unclear and poorly organized; difficult to understand the main point.

2 = Good: Some clarity, but organization is inconsistent; the main point may be obscured by less relevant details.

3 = Very Good: Ideas are mostly clear and organized, with a logical progression that supports understanding.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are very clear and well-organized; the writing presents a strong, coherent message that is easy to follow.

3. Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Clarity and Development: Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

1 = Needs Improvement: Lacks clarity and detail; ideas are underdeveloped and difficult to understand.

2 = Good: Ideas are somewhat clear, but supporting details are limited or not fully developed.

3 = Very Good: Ideas are clear with adequate supporting details that enhance understanding.

4 = Excellent: Ideas are clear and well-developed; supporting details are relevant, thorough, and effectively enhance the main points.

4. Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Qualitative Reflection Questions

This section collects teachers' insights on the organization, cohesion, and clarity of the student's writing sample. Feedback will highlight strengths and areas for improvement prior to the intervention.

5. Describe how the student organizes and connects their ideas in this writing sample.
6. What specific strengths or areas for improvement do you notice in the student's writing?
7. How effectively does the student use transitions to enhance cohesion?

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Appendix J

Grade 8 - Post AI Intervention Writing

Sample: Narrative

Thank you for participating in this study! This form is part of a qualitative research project assessing the impact of AI tools on writing cohesion and organization. Please use the following rubric to evaluate the s

Writing Prompt for Student Submission

1. In a narrative essay (150-200 words), recount an event when you faced a challenge that tested your self-confidence. Describe the situation and what made it difficult for you. How did you feel during this time? Explain how you worked to overcome the challenge and what you learned from the experience. Be sure to include details about your thoughts and feelings to make your story engaging.

Rubric for Teacher Evaluation

Cohesion: Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample..

- 1 = Needs Improvement: Transitions are lacking or unclear; ideas are poorly connected, making the text difficult to follow.
- 2 = Good: Some transitions are used, but connections between ideas may be awkward or insufficient, leading to minor confusion.
- 3 = Very Good: Ideas flow logically with appropriate transitions, demonstrating good organization and connection.
- 4 = Excellent: Ideas are seamlessly connected with excellent use of transitions, resulting in clear and engaging writing.

2. Rate the use of transitions and logical flow between ideas in the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Coherence: Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

- 1 = Needs Improvement: Ideas are unclear and poorly organized; difficult to understand the main point.
- 2 = Good: Some clarity, but organization is inconsistent; the main point may be obscured by less relevant details.
- 3 = Very Good: Ideas are mostly clear and organized, with a logical progression that supports understanding.
- 4 = Excellent: Ideas are very clear and well-organized; the writing presents a strong, coherent message that is easy to follow.

3. Rate the clarity of ideas and overall organization of the writing sample.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Clarity and Development: Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

- 1** = Needs Improvement: Lacks clarity and detail; ideas are underdeveloped and difficult to understand.
- 2** = Good: Ideas are somewhat clear, but supporting details are limited or not fully developed.
- 3** = Very Good: Ideas are clear with adequate supporting details that enhance understanding.
- 4** = Excellent: Ideas are clear and well-developed; supporting details are relevant, thorough, and effectively enhance the main points.

4. Rate the clarity of ideas and the level of detail in supporting information.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4

Qualitative Reflection Questions

This section collects teachers' insights on the organization, cohesion, and clarity of the student's writing sample. Feedback will highlight strengths and areas for improvement prior to the intervention.

5. Describe how the student organizes and connects their ideas in this writing sample.
6. What specific strengths or areas for improvement do you notice in the student's writing?
7. |How effectively does the student use transitions to enhance cohesion?
8. What impact do you think the use of AI tools had on this writing sample?
9. Were there any notable improvements or regressions compared to previous writing samples?
10. How well does the student convey their main idea or argument throughout the piece?

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Appendix K

Exploring the Impact of AI Writing Tools on Student Writing Cohesion: Teacher Perspectives

Thank you for participating in this study. This form is part of a qualitative study seeking teachers' insights on the impact of AI writing tools on the cohesion and organization in students' writing. Your responses are confidential and will contribute to understanding the educational implications of AI-assisted writing. This survey will take approximately 10-15 minutes.

Indicates required question

Background Information

Please include your experience specifically with teaching English or writing if applicable

1. How long have you been teaching, and what subjects do you teach?

Observations of AI Tool Usage

Include any observations on specific tools and how frequently students use them

2. Have you observed your students using AI writing tools? If so, in what ways do you see these tools being used?

Perceived Impact on Writing Cohesion

Describe any changes you've noticed in students' writing, structure, or idea development.

3. From your perspective, how have AI tools influenced students' ability to organize and connect ideas in writing? Do you see any specific patterns or trends?
4. Can you provide examples of instances where AI writing tools have either helped or hindered students' writing cohesion?
5. What challenges or benefits do you believe AI tools introduce to students' writing processes?

Additional Feedback

This could include your thoughts on how these tools might shape writing instruction or any suggestions for how to guide students in using AI responsibly.

6. Are there any additional comments you would like to share on the role of AI tools in student learning or writing development?

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Appendix L

Exploring the Effect of AI Writing Tools on Writing Cohesion (Student Survey)

Thank you for participating in this study! This survey is part of a study that explores how AI writing tools, like Grammarly and ChatGPT, impact how students organize and connect ideas in their writing. Your responses are completely confidential and will help us understand how these tools affect writing skills. The survey should take around 10-15 minutes to complete.

Indicates required question

Participant Information

1. Age
Mark only one oval.
11-12
12-13 13-14 other
2. Grade
Mark only one oval.
Grade 7
Grade 8

Skip to question 3

AI Tool Usage Experience

Feel free to mention specific tools and situations in which you use them

3. Describe how frequently you use AI writing tools (e.g., Grammarly, ChatGPT, or other tools).
What motivates you to use them, or why do you choose not to?

Skip to question 3

Impact of AI on Writing Cohesion

Describe any specific ways these tools have influenced how you connect or organize ideas in your writing.

4. In what ways, if any, do you feel AI writing tools have helped you improve the flow of ideas in your writing?
5. Can you share an example of a recent time when using an AI writing tool affected how do you structure or clarify your writing? Think of a specific assignment or piece of writing and describe any changes AI tools helped you make.
6. What challenges have you experienced while using AI writing tools? Do you feel these tools sometimes make it harder to write clearly or organize your ideas?

Additional Feedback

This could include any other ways these tools have impacted your writing or any thoughts you have on using AI in school.

7. Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience using AI tools for writing?

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Appendix M

Post-Focus Group Feedback Survey

Thank you again for your participation in the focus group! Your feedback is essential to understanding your experiences with AI writing tools and the focus group session itself. This survey is confidential and will allow you to share any further reflections. It should take about 5-10 minutes to complete.

Indicates required question

Reflection on AI Writing Tools

1. Since the focus group, have you thought of any additional ways in which AI writing tools impact your writing cohesion or organization of ideas?
2. How would you describe the effect (positive or negative) that AI tools have on your ability to express ideas clearly and connect them in your writing?
3. Are there any specific challenges or benefits related to AI tools in writing that you didn't mention during the focus group but would like to share now?

Focus Group Experience

4. How did you feel about the focus group session as a way to discuss and reflect on your experiences with AI writing tools?
5. What aspects of the focus group made you feel comfortable or encouraged you to share your thoughts?
6. Did the focus group session prompt you to think differently or more deeply about how you use AI tools in your writing? Please explain.
7. What suggestions do you have for improving the focus group format to encourage even better discussion and reflection?

Final Reflections

8. Are there any other thoughts, ideas, or reflections you'd like to add about the focus group, AI tools, or the study overall?

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Appendix N

Approval page from IRB at LIU

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